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Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan –
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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

List of project participants

Participant organisation name	Country
Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS)	PT
St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS)	AT
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)	HU
Politehnica University of Timisoara (UPT)	RO
University Colleges Leuven Limburg (UCLL)	BE
Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (ViA)	LV

Abbreviated terms

ARENA – Platform of E³UDRES² Alliance

E³UDRES² – Engaged and Entrepreneurial European University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions

EA – Exploitation Activities

ECSA – European Citizen Science Association

EU – European Union

CS – Citizen Science

CSA – Coordination and Support Action

KER – Key Exploitable Results

OA – Open Access

OE – Open Education

OI – Open Innovation

OS – Open Science

RD&I – Research, Development and Innovation

WP – Work Package

Executive Summary

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project is a collaborative initiative aimed at refining a joint research and innovation strategy and a unified agenda. Its ambition is to strengthen E³UDRES² as a European multi-institutional Research and Innovation Hub focused on Smart and Sustainable Regions.

This deliverable summarises the main achievements of the project during its second reporting period (M16–M36). It brings together evidence of activities and results in dissemination, exploitation and communication, following the strategy defined in D1.2 (Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan).

Key achievements include:

- Use of project and institutional channels to reach the target groups and objectives defined in the D1.2 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.
- 433 social media posts across LinkedIn, Facebook, X and YouTube. The metrics defined in the Grant Agreement (visits and likes) were achieved and in some cases went beyond the defined targets.
- The project website proved to be a main tool for communication and dissemination, registering 5628 visits and a total of 8,144 downloads, with deliverables being the most downloaded documents.
- Publication of five project newsletters during this period.
- Participation of five Ent-r-e-novators institutions in the European Researchers' Night.
- Organisation of the final Conference of the project, the Science Policy Conference, gathering institutions, stakeholders and external participants.

Overall, communication remained the central focus of this period, while dissemination activities increased progressively, and exploitation will be intensified in the final project phase. The metrics defined in the Grant Agreement (visits and likes) were consistently exceeded.

1. Tasks

Task T.1.4 Project communication dissemination and exploitation plan (IPS, all participants)

M1-M36

Task leader: IPS

Contributors: All partners

Task T1.4 defined the project's plan for communication, dissemination, and exploitation (M1–M36). This plan, whose deliverable was submitted in M6, guided the work carried out over the subsequent 30 months. The activities described in this report align with those outlined in Deliverable D1.2 and cover the period from month 16 to month 36. The first 15 months had already been reported in Deliverable D1.5 – Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Report – part 1.

Taken together, the three deliverables reflect the progressive development of communication, dissemination and exploitation. Deliverable D1.2, prepared at the outset, established the strategic framework and objectives. Deliverable D1.5 illustrated and described the channels, tools and communication outputs created in the initial phase, when much of the effort was focused on implementing the plan. Deliverable D1.8, prepared at the closing stage of the project, focuses on analysing results, a reflection that is most relevant when assessing the project's overall impact.

2. Communication and dissemination activities

This chapter provides an overview of the project's communication and dissemination activities during the second reporting period. It highlights the methodology used to collect and analyse data, the scale of activities carried out, and their contribution to the project's objectives. The results show strong growth compared to the first period, reflecting greater visibility, stronger engagement with target audiences, and the achievement of the metrics set in the Grant Agreement.

2.1. Methodological note on data collection and analysis

The analysis of communication and dissemination activities combines quantitative data with qualitative interpretation. Numbers show the scale of actions, while contextual analysis explains their contribution to project objectives and milestones. This approach avoids reducing communication to simple counts and underlines its role in supporting broader results.

A range of digital tools supported the preparation of this deliverable. Excel was used as the main instrument for recording and organising activities, and several graphs were generated with

integrated visualisation tools. For data collection, content management and social media platforms were also used, such as Joomla, Buffer and the analytics dashboards of each social network. AI-based tools — ChatGPT (OpenAI), Grammarly and Google Translate — supported parts of the English translation and revision. They were used only to improve precision and clarity, always under the supervision and validation of the WP1 coordination team, ensuring methodological coherence and full intellectual authorship of the document.

The analysis presented here is based on:

- The systematic registration of communication and dissemination actions in a dedicated “tracker” file. This instrument documented activities carried out directly through the project’s channels, as well as external actions identified during the reporting period. While not every activity can be fully documented, since external communication often depends on traceable evidence, the tracker provides a structured and reliable overview.

Given the higher frequency and volume of activity on social media and the website during the second reporting period, data were complemented by additional sources to ensure accuracy and comparability:

- Website data were obtained through the Joomla content management system (site administration platform) and from reports provided by Albatroz Digital, the company responsible for hosting and technical maintenance. Two timeframes were considered — from 1 October 2022 to 31 December 2023, and from 1 January 2024 to 27 September 2025 — covering the project’s full 36 months and allowing comparisons between reporting periods.
- Social media data (Facebook, LinkedIn, X/Twitter and YouTube) were collected from multiple sources:
 - Buffer, the tool adopted for managing Facebook, LinkedIn and X/Twitter.
 - Facebook data extracted from both Buffer and Meta Business Suite, complete for both periods (with the exception of views, available only for 2025).
 - LinkedIn data combining Buffer exports and native LinkedIn analytics, which provide only the last 365 days due to platform limitations.
 - For X/Twitter, as only premium accounts allow full historical exports, the first reporting period was reconstructed manually from archived posts, while the second was extracted directly from Buffer.

For comparability, the analysis focused on metrics consistently available across platforms:

- number of posts;

- impressions;
- likes and other interactions;
- new followers.

Indicators not uniformly accessible (such as comments, shares or link clicks) were excluded from cross-platform comparison tables, though they were taken into account in the specific interpretations of each platform.

This combined approach sometimes produced totals slightly higher than those recorded in the tracker (manual recording is more prone to error), providing a more accurate representation of actual activity. Despite the inherent limitations of each platform, the combination of systematic recording and complementary statistics ensured a robust and comparable dataset. This provides a reliable basis for assessing the evolution of communication and dissemination activities across both reporting periods.

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2.2. Results overview

During this second reporting period (January 2024 to September 2025), a total of 985 communication and dissemination activities were recorded, compared with 219 in the first period. This represents an increase of 766 actions (about 350%), confirming the transition from an initial set-up phase to a more consolidated stage of the project.

This strong growth reflects a more consolidated stage of the project, with more results available for dissemination and broader interactions with external audiences. Project visibility benefited from stronger partnerships - including cluster projects - and from a refined methodology for registering and categorising activities. These improvements enabled the capture of a wider range of actions and more effective tracking of earned media compared with the initial phase.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the monthly activity volumes in the second reporting period reveal several high-impact peaks. These were not incidental: they reflect a strategy aimed at maximising visibility at moments of greater relevance in the project timeline.

The most prominent peaks correspond to the Science and Policy Conference (May 2025, IPS, Portugal) and the PhD Summer School (June 2025, UPT, Romania). Both were flagship initiatives of Ent-r-e-novators and generated intense communication flows across social media, institutional

websites and partner platforms. These efforts ensured broad attention from both internal and external audiences and consolidated the project’s public profile.

Figure 1 - Monthly activity volume in the second reporting period

Peaks were also visible around the release of Newsletters 3, 5 and 6. Each newsletter was treated as a dissemination output in its own right and supported by a small communication plan involving social media posts, dedicated website articles, email circulation and additional promotion through the E³UDRES² alliance. This ensured that newsletters were not only published but also shared, accessed and downloaded. A good example is the release of Newsletters 5 and 6 in July 2025, which helped sustain communication activity despite the usual slowdown in the academic summer break.

Other milestones also contributed to raising activity levels. The Open Science and Education Workshop hosted by UCLL in March 2024 was the first clear peak of this period. Newsletter 3, published in June 2024, generated another visible increase, while Newsletter 4 in September 2024 helped maintain awareness in the run-up to the final project year. In March 2025, the Open Education and Science Practices Workshop organised by ViA University created another rise in activity, mainly through social media and institutional communication.

The most intense sequence occurred between May and July 2025, when the Science and Policy Conference, the PhD Summer School and the release of Newsletters 5 and 6 combined to sustain high volumes of communication and dissemination during the project’s closing phase.

Looking at the project as a whole, the most visible spikes were linked to major events and newsletter releases, showing that outreach activity was strongest whenever milestones were reached and results were ready to be shared.

Connection between communication and dissemination

During the second reporting period, 985 activities were recorded in the categories of communication and dissemination. Of these, 848 were classified as communication and 137 as dissemination. The overall distribution is illustrated in Figure 2, which shows the predominance of communication actions, while also reflecting the increasing importance of dissemination.

Figure 2 - Distribution of communication and dissemination activities

Figure 3 shows that the dissemination peaks were also directly linked to major project-organised events and the release of newsletters. The Open Science and Education Workshop hosted by UCLL in March 2024 marked the first peak, followed by Newsletter 3 in June 2024 and Newsletter 4 in September 2024. In March 2025, dissemination intensified again with the Open Education and Science Practices Workshop organised by ViA University. The strongest peaks occurred in May and June 2025, corresponding respectively to the Science and Policy Conference at IPS in Portugal and the PhD Summer School in Timișoara, Romania. A final peak was observed in July 2025 with the release of newsletters 5 and 6.

Figure 3 - Connection between Communication and Dissemination (monthly distribution across M16-M36)

In all these cases, dissemination outputs were systematically accompanied by a larger volume of communication actions, including social media posts, website articles, press releases and visibility materials. This confirms that newsletters, deliverables and events were rarely stand-alone actions, but rather triggers for broader communication campaigns aimed at amplifying reach and ensuring visibility among diverse audiences. The data, therefore, highlights a deliberate and consistent pattern: whenever dissemination intensified, communication activity expanded in parallel, reinforcing both reach and impact.

When comparing the two reporting periods, the evolution of activities reflects the expected trajectory of the project Figure 4. In the initial evaluation period, communication was predominant, as it was essential to give visibility to the project and create initial recognition, while the work packages were just beginning their activities and had not yet produced significant dissemination outputs. Dissemination remained almost absent during this phase, with the exception of a small peak in March 2023, mainly linked to the second General Assembly and the initial workshops of the work packages. Communication also grew slowly in this early stage, with its first notable peak in March 2023, driven by the project’s press release, media coverage, the launch of institutional materials, and intensified activity across social media channels.

Figure 4 - Evolution of communication and dissemination activities across the 36 months of the project

As anticipated, the second reporting period, beginning in January 2024 and highlighted by the green line on the right side of the Figure 4 represented a turning point. Dissemination activities became more consistent as the work packages delivered results and approved deliverables provided concrete content to share. Multiple peaks were recorded, reflecting major project events, newsletters, and academic contributions. This growth in dissemination between months 16 and 36 was accompanied by a parallel increase in communication actions, ensuring that the knowledge generated by the project was effectively shared and reached diverse audiences.

The data therefore demonstrates a coherent progression: initial communication actions built the project’s presence, while the second period consolidated this foundation by combining stronger dissemination with intensified communication.

2.2.1 Communication and dissemination channels/targets

The distinction between communication and dissemination followed the framework established in Deliverable D1.2, which defined the objectives, target groups and channels for each dimension. Table 1, below, summarises the channels most frequently used during the second reporting period and the audiences reached.

In practice, the most active communication channels have evolved over time. During the first reporting period, activity was primarily focused on social media and the project website, which played a crucial role in establishing initial awareness and maintaining visibility beyond the consortium. In the second reporting period, these channels remained important but were complemented by more systematic use of newsletters, press releases and open events, which reinforced engagement with local citizens, students, regional stakeholders and the media.

Table 1 - Communication and dissemination channels & targets

Communication		Dissemination	
Frequently used channels	Primary targets	Frequently used channels	Primary targets
Project/partners social media Project/partner websites Project/partner newsletters Press releases Open events and event's presentations	Partners communities Regional Stakeholders Local Citizens Pre-college, undergraduate and graduate students News media	Project/partners social media (YouTube/streaming videos) Project/partners websites Open reports, deliverables and publications Conference and other events Surveys Workshops Presentations result-focused Newsletters Classes Streaming platform	Scientific community Citizens and civil society Policy and decision makers Other European University Alliances and HEIs

The communication and dissemination messages were aligned with the objectives defined in D1.2 (Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan). While the specific wording varied depending on context, the overall approach aimed to:

- For **partner communities and regional stakeholders**: raise awareness of project goals, progress and opportunities for engagement.
- For the **scientific community and policy makers**: emphasise results, relevance for European research and innovation agendas, and policy impact.
- For **students, citizens and society**: present the project in accessible language, highlight opportunities to participate, and show concrete benefits of citizen science.

For dissemination, the website and public deliverables served as the primary vehicles throughout the project, ensuring open and consistent access to project outputs. During the second reporting period, however, their role was strengthened by conferences, workshops and streaming videos, notably the flagship Science & Policy Conference and the PhD Summer School, which created opportunities for direct interaction with the scientific community, policy-makers and other higher education institutions.

This progression shows that the project followed the strategy outlined in D1.2, adjusting the use of channels according to context and maturity. In the early phase, visibility relied on flexible and fast channels, while in the later phase, dissemination activities gained prominence, ensuring that results were not only communicated but also anchored in practices and policies.

2.2.2 Communication channels and activities

In the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (Deliverable D1.2), the project defined a set of channels in line with the Grant Agreement. These included social media, the website, newsletters, press releases, institutional news, events and workshops, presentations, the video series, the final conference, and participation in the partner institutions' European Researchers' Night. Together, these channels were designed to cover both internal communication, supporting coordination within the consortium, and external communication, targeting academic, institutional and wider audiences.

As shown in Figure 5 social media accounted for the largest share with 609 actions in the second period, confirming its role as the main tool for visibility and engagement. The website followed with 241 actions, reflecting the regular publication of articles, event announcements and public deliverables. Newsletters (15) and press releases (24) complemented these digital channels, while 26 media news items further expanded the project's presence in external outlets.

Figure 5 - Communication actions by channels by reporting period and total

In-person and hybrid places of activity (61) also played a relevant role. The project organised or contributed to 19 events and workshops, as well as 24 presentations. The conference category includes a single event – the Science and Policy Conference, held on 13 May 2025 at IPS – which

was planned from the outset as the project's flagship event. Additional activities were captured under "other" (16), including contributions to meetings and dissemination through partner platforms.

The comparison across periods highlights the transition from a start-up phase to a mature stage. In the first period, most activity focused on building the website, launching social media and introducing the project. In the second period, communication became more systematic, with larger volumes across all channels and stronger emphasis on dissemination and interaction. This confirms that the channels originally defined in the plan were maintained and mobilised to support visibility and the uptake of results.

Social Media

During the project, social media channels became one of the most effective tools for visibility and engagement. LinkedIn was the most dynamic platform, generating the highest growth in followers and serving as the main source of visits to the project website. Facebook retained its role as a broad outreach tool for a wider audience, while YouTube developed more slowly but provided a permanent archive of workshops and events. In the second reporting period, project accounts published 433 posts and recorded 37495 impressions and 6943 interactions, confirming that the targets set in the Grant Agreement were not only met but substantially exceeded.

Social media played a central role in the Ent-r-e-novators' communication strategy. It offered fast and flexible channels to reach academic, institutional and wider audiences. The analysis in this section refers only to the project's own accounts on Facebook, X, LinkedIn and YouTube. These formed the backbone of activity, although partners, cluster projects and associated networks also contributed with posts that are not included here.

The four Ent-r-e-novators channels, created on 29 March 2023, remained active throughout the project. In the second reporting period (M16–M36), they generated 433 posts and uploads. Most activity took place on Facebook, X and LinkedIn, while YouTube played a more focused role as the repository for video content. On average, this meant around five posts each week, with clear peaks around major project events and slower periods during academic breaks. In addition to these, 176 reinforcement actions were disseminated through the social media channels of partner institutions and associated networks, expanding the project's reach beyond its own accounts.

Compared with the first reporting period (111 posts), the growth is evident. The number of posts increased by around 290%, and the monthly average rose from 12 to 21. Across the full 36 months, this amounts to 544 actions in total. While the early posts introduced the project and built initial visibility, the later ones had a stronger focus on dissemination, promoting deliverables, newsletters, videos and events. Content also became more tailored to each platform. LinkedIn, for example,

was used for carousel posts and more detailed presentations, and proved to be the main driver of visits to the website.

The impact of social media activity is reflected in the growth of reach, interactions and followers across all platforms. For comparability, the analysis of “views” in this report is based on impressions (content displays), which provide a consistent metric across platforms.

During the second reporting period, project accounts generated:

- 37495 impressions/visits, corresponding to an average of 1785 impressions/visits per month (Grant Agreement target – 20 visits/month);
- corresponding to an average of 138 likes per month (Grant Agreement target – 10 likes/month);
- 2872 link clicks¹;
- 1015 comments¹;
- 338 shares.

In total (likes, comments, shares, and link clicks), 6943 interactions with published content were recorded across the project’s social media accounts, confirming that posts were not only displayed but also actively engaged with. Within these interactions, LinkedIn stood out as the project’s main channel, accounting for 5690 interactions.

The analysis confirms that the four channels complemented each other, with each finding its own role in the project’s communication. LinkedIn proved most effective for professional audiences, Facebook reached wider publics, X added timeliness, and YouTube provided a long-term archive. Together, they formed a balanced online presence that supported both visibility and dissemination.

[X \(formerly Twitter\)](#)

X was used in line with the project’s other social media channels, following a consistent approach to posting news, updates and links to project activities. It complemented the presence on Facebook and LinkedIn, contributing to the overall visibility of the project online and ensuring that project information reached audiences across different platforms

¹ Facebook and YouTube data were not available.

Figure 6 - X metrics in the first and second reporting periods

As shown in Figure 6, the channel recorded higher activity and results in the second reporting period: 122 tweets, 1531 impressions, 28 likes, 5 shares, 21 link clicks, 17 comments, 82 engagements and 4 new followers. Although the absolute values remain modest compared with other platforms, they show a clear increase in posting frequency, reach and engagement on X. This growth reflects the project's more established identity during the second reporting period and a more systematic approach to maintaining an online presence.

The first reporting period served as a baseline, with 24 tweets, 264 impressions and 20 likes. This starting point makes the progression visible, from a limited initial footprint to a more consistent presence in the second period. X remained the least impactful of the project's social media channels, but it still provided an additional space to disseminate information and reinforce visibility alongside Facebook and LinkedIn.

Facebook

Moving from X to one of the project's main channels, Facebook was used consistently throughout the project and served as a primary space for interaction with wider audiences. It supported the dissemination of news, event announcements, deliverables and highlights, and acted as a link between institutional activities and public communication.

As illustrated in Figure 7, activity on Facebook intensified considerably in the second reporting period (M16–M36). A total of 143 posts were published, compared with 31 in the first period, representing an increase of 361%. The average monthly frequency rose from around three posts to almost seven, showing a more systematic use of the channel.

Figure 7- Facebook metrics in the first and second reporting periods

This higher level of activity translated into stronger audience engagement. Content interactions rose from 68 in the first period to a combined total of 1363 in the second period (750 likes, 613 shares), suggesting not only a larger audience but also greater responsiveness to the content shared. Visits increased from 217 to 1506, showing that more users were motivated to explore the page. New followers also increased, from 16 to 38, consolidating a base of recurring contacts.

Taken together, the data presented in Figure 7 show that Facebook moved beyond its initial role as a supplementary channel in the first period to become a more relevant space for communication in the second. The higher volume of posts and growth in all engagement metrics indicate the channel's importance in amplifying the visibility of project outputs and activities.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn was the project's most frequently used social media channel, fully aligned with the professional audiences addressed by the project. It consistently disseminated updates, announced events, highlighted achievements and shared deliverables. Its audience corresponded to the project's focus on higher education institutions, open science and open education, attracting researchers, teaching staff, project managers and other stakeholders active in innovation and capacity building.

During the second reporting period, the project published 143 posts, which generated in the last 365 days²:

- 28313 impressions;

² As outlined in the methodological note, the data for LinkedIn are available only for the last 365 days.

- 1983 likes;
- 397 shares;
- 438 comments;
- 2872 link clicks.

The channel also attracted 197 new followers, bringing the overall number of followers to 314. These numbers confirm LinkedIn an important space for engaging a professional and institutionally oriented audience and for consolidating visibility and credibility among its target groups. Interaction levels reflect the platform’s specialised nature, with content resonating strongly with higher education professionals and decision-makers.

Figure 8 - LinkedIn metrics in the first and second reporting periods

Compared with the first reporting period (Figure 8), when 25 posts were published and 330 likes recorded, the progression is clear. LinkedIn also registered steady growth in its follower base, from 117 to 314, further consolidating its role as the main driver for reaching higher education professionals, sharing open practices and signalling opportunities across the project’s platforms.

Youtube

YouTube was exclusively dedicated to the project’s dissemination. It served mainly as a repository for video content – such as interviews, recordings of events and short thematic clips - rather than as a platform for frequent posting or real-time updates. This explains the lower numbers recorded overall and the more irregular posting rhythm, while also highlighting its importance as a permanent library of audiovisual resources.

During the second reporting period, the channel registered a clear increase in activity. A total of 24 videos were published, compared with 8 in the first period. The channel also received 23 likes and 13 new subscribers, compared with 11 likes and 3 subscribers in the first reporting period.

The number of video views remained stable, rising slightly from 377 to 390, while impressions increased substantially from 387 to 6145. The divergence between impressions and views illustrates YouTube's specific role in dissemination:

- Impressions – the number of times video thumbnails were displayed in search results, recommendations or user feeds – rose from 387 to 6145, showing that project content gained far greater visibility on the platform.
- Views – the number of times users actually opened and watched the videos – remained stable at around 390.

This means that the conversion rate, i.e. the percentage of people exposed to the thumbnails who actually watched the videos, stayed relatively constant. This is natural, since the conversion depends on the attractiveness of the title, the thumbnail and the immediate relevance for the viewer. In a project with such a specific scope, content will only capture the attention of a more specialised audience.

Turning now to the content published, to ensure clarity and facilitate navigation, the videos were organised thematically into playlists:

1. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Events (5 videos, all published in this period);
2. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Video Series (9 videos in total, 6 published in this period);
3. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Science & Policy Conference | Thematic Corners (7 videos, all published in this period);
4. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Interviews (5 videos, all published in the first period);
5. Knowledge clips | Creating Communities, Engaging Citizens, and Society (5 videos, all published in this period).

Together, these playlists comprise 32 videos with complementary themes and perspectives. Of these, the 24 videos released during the second reporting period averaged 31 views each. Overall, the video outputs provided the project with dynamic content formats that complemented written materials, enhanced dissemination efforts, and diversified the ways in which results were shared with different audiences.

Geographical distribution

LinkedIn data provides the only available basis for analysing the geographical reach of the Ent-r-e-novators project. As the project’s largest social media channel – with the highest number of followers, likes, and impressions – it offers the most robust dataset, while comparable demographic data from other platforms or the website was not accessible due to restrictions for reporting.

Figure 9 - Geographical distribution of LinkedIn followers (from the last 365 Days)

Figure 9 illustrates the geographical distribution of the project’s LinkedIn followers. Although these numbers reflect only LinkedIn users, and usage patterns of the platform may differ between countries and audiences, they give a valuable indication of the project’s visibility at the European level. They also demonstrate how communications resonate differently across regions, providing valuable insights for future outreach strategies. For this reason, and despite their limitations, the LinkedIn data are presented here as an example of the project’s international audience.

Website

During the second reporting period, the website consolidated its role as a central hub for communication and dissemination. It combined timely communication (news and announcements) with systematic dissemination of deliverables, newsletters, conference materials and videos, as well as complementary functions such as articles, downloads and referral links.

In this period, the site registered 5628 visits, meaning that this number of users accessed the website. Together, these visits generated 11728 page views, that is, the total number of pages opened. On average, each visit involved viewing more than two pages, which indicates that users

did not remain on the entry page — whether homepage, a specific event page or a direct link from social media — but continued to navigate through other sections of the site. This behaviour shows that the website was used not only as a point of access but also as a source of further exploration of project content.

Figure 10 - Evolution of website views across the 2^o period of the project

Figure 10 illustrates how visits evolved during the second reporting period, with peaks coinciding with major milestones such as the Science and Policy Conference, the PhD Summer School in Timisoara, workshops, and the release of several newsletters. These peaks demonstrate that audiences returned to the site whenever new content was published.

User behaviour also shifted between the two periods. Initially, visitors tended to spend more time on the site and move across several sections to learn about the project. In the second, visits became shorter and more focused, often directed to specific deliverables, newsletters or event information, frequently through links shared on social media, search engines or partner websites.

Over the 36-month project period, the site accumulated 6976 visits and 15303 page views. The monthly average of visits increased from 36 in the first period to 248 in the second, well above the baseline of 10 visits per month defined in the Grant Agreement.

It would have been valuable to complement these statistics with information about visitor profiles, geographical distribution or demographics, as this would have enabled a more detailed analysis of audience engagement. However, such data were not available from the website administrator. For this reason, LinkedIn analytics were used as a complementary source, since they provide more granular insights into reach and interaction.

Articles and news

During this reporting period, 32 new articles were published in the news and video sections, gathering a total of 20861 visits. As shown in Figure 11, the most accessed content was directly linked to events, with the announcement of the Science and Policy Conference reaching 3303 visits. Other highly accessed items included workshop announcements and newsletters. This pattern suggests that articles acted as entry points, guiding audiences to the project’s milestones and reinforcing the connection between online content and offline activities.

Figure 11 - Articles published on the website with the highest number of views

Documents and downloads

In the same period, 54 new documents were uploaded, including public deliverables, newsletters, event programmes and presentations. Across the 36 months of the project, a total of 10722 downloads were recorded³, with a monthly average of 286. Downloads were especially strong for public deliverables and conference materials (Figure 12). Deliverables alone reached 3651 downloads, averaging more than 400 per file, while the five press releases together generated close to 1000 downloads. These figures confirm that the website worked as a channel for visibility and also as a repository of practical resources procured by the project’s targets.

³ The number of downloads presented in the website statistics refers to cumulative downloads, as no data separated by reporting period is available.

Figure 12 - Downloads of documents published on the website

Traffic sources

The analysis of referral channels showed in Figure 13, highlights the diversification of access to the website. Direct visits continued to represent the largest share (62.6%), but search engines became much more prominent, with over 1100 sessions compared to only 158 in the first period. Social media referrals also grew fivefold to 94 visits, with LinkedIn, Facebook and X all contributing. Outbound links from the site – connecting users to partner institutions, clustering initiatives and event pages – multiplied by almost five (+474%). This indicates that the website served not only as an access point for project content but also as a hub linking internal resources to wider ecosystems.

Figure 13 - Sources of website traffic overall assessment

Overall assessment

Taken together, the indicators confirm that the website evolved into a consolidated hub for both communication and dissemination. Traffic levels rose steadily, downloads of public deliverables were consistent, and referrals from search engines and social platforms became more significant. Compared with the first reporting period (M1–M15), the second shows stronger reach and engagement, particularly through search engine referrals, social media links and systematic use of the website for public deliverables. Growth was not only quantitative but also closely connected to project milestones, reflecting the deliberate integration of communication and dissemination in line with the project's strategy.

Newsletter

During this phase of the project, five newsletter editions were published. Together with the two editions released in the first reporting period, this brings the total to seven, one more than the originally foreseen six in the Grant Agreement. Most were issued in the second period, with three concentrated in the final months. This decision reflected the understanding that the closing stage would be particularly relevant for presenting work package outputs and approved public deliverables.

Each edition was published as a PDF on the dedicated newsletter page of the project website. To increase visibility, a corresponding article was also created in the news section. On social media, communication around each newsletter always began with a launch post announcing its publication, followed by four to five posts highlighting key topics from the edition (example in Figure 14). These topics were chosen as the most relevant for dissemination, ensuring that concrete results were reached by targeted audiences. In every case, posts and email announcements directed readers to the newsletter page on the website, also encouraging navigation to other sections.

Figure 14 - Example of highlights of the communication for Newsletter 7

Figure 12, about the number of downloads made through the website, showed help us to perceive that the newsletters generated steady levels of access and downloads, confirming their role as both communication and dissemination outputs. In total, they reached 3166 downloads across the 36 months of the project. Peaks can be linked to specific releases: Newsletter 3 in June 2024 and Newsletters 5 and 6 in July 2025, each triggered visible increases in online engagement. The timing of Newsletters 5 and 6 was particularly relevant — released during the summer academic break, they helped sustain project visibility in a period when communication normally slows down.

In addition to these peaks, the newsletters were consistently shared internally through the EMDESK platform and circulated by email to project participants, E³UDRES² communication officers, cluster projects and the subscriber list, which grew to 79 active subscribers.

The content of the newsletters combined short project updates, public deliverables, interviews with team members and stakeholders, collaborations with cluster projects and event highlights. While communication-oriented articles dominated the first editions, the focus gradually shifted towards dissemination-related content as more results became available.

Looking across the full 36 months of the project, newsletters proved to be an effective tool for combining communication and dissemination. They ensured regular visibility while also highlighting

concrete outcomes and collaborations at decisive moments, reinforcing the project's presence both within the consortium and among wider audiences.

Press releases

Press releases were used throughout the project to ensure that news about milestones and results reached both academic and wider audiences. In total, five releases were published by the Ent-r-e-novators coordination team during the second reporting period, complementing the two issued in the first. Together, these seven press releases addressed key project moments, such as the launch of the video series, the announcement of the Science and Policy Conference, and the dissemination of public deliverables.

In parallel, partner institutions amplified the project's visibility by producing and circulating additional releases through their own communication offices. Twenty-four institutional press releases were identified during the second reporting period, covering topics such as workshops, events, training sessions and local dissemination initiatives. These were particularly relevant because they mobilised the communication structures of universities and regional stakeholders, extending the project's reach well beyond its own channels.

The five project-level press releases together generated nearly 1000 downloads, confirming that they were not only read but also actively used as references by different audiences. The institutional releases were also published on university websites, shared on their social media accounts and, in some cases, picked up by regional news media. This demonstrates the multiplier effect achieved when institutional and project communication were aligned.

The content of the press releases combined visibility-oriented news with more substantive messages. Several focused on highlighting concrete results, such as approved deliverables or the launch of new tools, while others announced events or gave visibility to collaborations with cluster projects. In all cases, they were designed to be easily adapted and reused by communication officers in partner institutions, increasing their chances of circulation and reuse.

The experience with press releases and newsletters illustrates the importance of a multichannel approach. Each release was prepared as a stand-alone document but was also connected to other communication tools. They were published on the project website, shared through social media posts, and circulated by email to specific mailing lists. In this way, press releases acted as starting points for broader communication flows, amplifying visibility through institutional and external channels.

Video series

The production of a video series was foreseen in the Grant Agreement, with the commitment to deliver nine short videos (three per project year). Throughout the project's implementation, additional videos were considered relevant for dissemination purposes. All videos were made available on the project's YouTube channel and embedded on the project website. Each publication was accompanied by a dedicated post on the three project social media platforms, where the link systematically directed audiences to the website, encouraging further navigation across its pages. Whenever videos were released close to the launch of a newsletter, this channel also contributed to the wider dissemination of the videos.

The six video series published in this period, presentations from WP1 to WP6, complemented by a contribution from Hannes Raffaseder (STPUAS), Lead of the E³UDRES² alliance, highlighting the strategic importance of the project's results to the alliance, and a video from Luísa Carvalho (IPS), Vice-President for Research and Internationalisation, reflecting on the project's impact at institutional level. The release of the Science & Policy Conference video in March 2025, which included presentations of results from each WP, was a good complement to the video series.

Meeting agendas/minutes

Meeting agendas and minutes were consistently prepared for the Work Package meetings, as well as for the General Assemblies and Executive Board meetings. These documents were shared by email with the respective WP teams, WP leads, and the IPS coordination team, and were also made available on the EMDESK platform in the dedicated folders of each work package. Beyond their operational function, they also served as an official record of decisions and as a tool to promote accountability and transparency within the project.

EMDESK

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project continued to rely on EMDESK as its central project management platform throughout the second reporting period. Beyond supporting administrative coordination, the platform functioned as the main repository for finalised project documents, also enabling that information was consistently available to all partners.

Each work package maintained dedicated folders where agendas, meeting minutes, event presentations, workshop materials, videos or podcasts, completed working documents, and deliverables were systematically stored. In addition, WP1 utilised specific folders to organise files related to project management and dissemination activities. This structure guaranteed that records were kept up to date and could be easily accessed by all teams whenever needed.

In this way, EMDESK complemented other communication channels by serving as a structured and reliable space for long-term storage and access, reinforcing transparency and continuity across the consortium.

Meetings

Project meetings continued to take place throughout the second reporting period, following the schedule and arrangements defined in the Grant Agreement. Regular coordination meetings were held between the IPS coordination team and the five WP leaders, as well as within WP teams, online via MS Teams, although other platforms, such as Zoom, were also used depending on the preferences of each WP. The General Assembly and Executive Board meetings maintained their biannual rhythm. Whenever possible, these meetings combined on-site participation of the coordination team, WP leaders, and representatives from the partner institutions with broader online attendance, ensuring the involvement of additional team members and relevant stakeholders.

Across the project's 36 months, each of the six institutions hosted at least one meeting. During this reporting period, meetings were organised by UPT, UCLL, and ViA, complementing the earlier ones held at IPS (kick-off), STPUAS, and MATE. The closing meeting occurred in late September 2025 at IPS.

Given that the project aims to contribute to the definition of strategies for the E³UDRES² alliance, two of the face-to-face meetings - the final one at IPS and the meeting at UPT in October 2024 - were held in parallel with E³UDRES² alliance assemblies. This allowed direct interaction with decision-makers and WPs of the alliance. In addition, the on-site meetings were often combined with dissemination opportunities, usually in the form of workshops hosted by the local institution in collaboration with WP1. These events brought together faculty and researchers from the host institution and, in hybrid formats, extended the project's reach to wider audiences.

Overall, the meetings not only ensured the regular coordination and governance of the project but also provided valuable opportunities for dissemination and engagement. By combining institutional hosting, hybrid participation, and links with E³UDRES² activities, they helped strengthen both the internal cohesion of the consortium and the visibility of the project in its broader academic and regional contexts.

Email

Email continued to be a fundamental tool for the project, particularly in ensuring communication between teams, individual members, and cluster projects, as had already been the case in the first reporting period. This channel was mainly used for organising work, scheduling meetings, sharing

access links, exchanging information, and disseminating project-related content, alongside other more routine matters. While primarily serving internal coordination, email also played a role in external visibility by supporting the distribution of newsletters and promoting events.

European Researchers' Night

In this period, the Ent-r-e-novators project was represented at the European Researchers' Night through activities organised by IPS, UPT, ViA, STPUAS, and MATE. While participation was coordinated among the project teams, the specific format of the presence at each site depended on the rules and decisions of the local organising committees. As a result, there were variations in location, type of stands, available spaces, and the audiences reached. Nevertheless, the use of shared printed and digital materials ensured a coherent representation of the project across the five institutions.

As this year's European Researchers' Night coincided with the project's closing meeting at IPS, the stand in Setúbal benefited from the presence of representatives from the partner institutions, further reinforcing the project's visibility.

As with the press releases, participation in the European Researchers' Night was not fully under the project's direct control, since final decisions rested with each host institution and the local coordination teams of the event. For this reason, the project was not represented at UCLL, despite the institution's membership in the consortium.

Others

Beyond the activities carried out through the website and social media, the project also relied on a wide range of direct engagements, including workshops, presentations, posters, webinars and public events. These opportunities provided visibility in diverse contexts, from international conferences to local initiatives organised by partner institutions.

Activities between months 16 and 36 involved school teachers, university students, researchers, regional stakeholders and the wider public. They ranged from experimental formats, such as the Junior Ent-r-e-novators pilot I-Living Lab summer camp, to more formal settings, like the EDEN Research Workshop or the International Week at STPUAS (Table 2). The repeated presence at the European Researchers' Night across all institutions reinforced the link between the project and broad citizen audiences.

Taken together, these events show how the Entr-e-n-ovators initiative expanded beyond the other channels already mentioned in this report, and became visible in academic, professional and civic environments. Each participation not only disseminated project goals and results but also created

spaces for interaction with different communities, helping to position the project within the broader ecosystem of the E³UDRES² alliance.

Table 2 - Presentation, showcase or reference at events

Activity	Description	Reason why	Month	Place	Target
Workshop for school teachers at VIA	Workshop for school teachers at VIA, April 12th 2024 (7 teachers participated)	Project dissemination and awareness	M19	ViA	School teachers
Event: Junior Ent-r-e-novators pilot I-Living Lab	Junior Ent-r-e-novators pilot I-Living Lab, a four-day Summer Camp called "Space Mission", July 2024 (24 children)	Project dissemination and awareness	M21	UCLL	
UCLL Poster	Poster about WP5 "E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Project"	Project dissemination and awareness	M23	UCLL	Entrenovators institutions and regions
Event: Citizen Science Networking Day 2024	Presence with a poster in a poster session at the Citizen Science Networking Day 2024	Project dissemination and awareness	M24	Lamot, Belgium	Scientific Community
European Researchers Night 2024 ViA	Activities with CS training at Scientist Night 2024, VIA September 27th, 2024, 15 participants	Project dissemination and awareness	M24	VIA	Regional Communities
European Researchers Night 2024 IPS	Project booth at European Researchers Night 2024	Project dissemination and awareness	M24	IPS	Entrenovators region
European Researchers Night 2024 MATE	Project booth at European Researchers Night 2024	Project dissemination and awareness	M24	MATE	Entrenovators region
European Researchers Night 2024 UPT	Project booth at European Researchers Night 2024	Project dissemination and awareness	M24	UPT	Entrenovators region
European Researchers Night 2024 STPUAS	Project booth at European Researchers Night 2024	Project dissemination and awareness	M24	STPUAS	Entrenovators region
Researchers' Night 2024 - STPUAS	Participation in the European Researchers' Night 2024"	Project dissemination and awareness	M24	STPUAS	STPUAS institution and regions
Open Campus Night	Participation in the European Researchers' Night 2024"	Project dissemination and awareness	M24	UPT	Politechnica University of Timisoara's community
Presentation about the objectives, results and outcomes of the project	Presentation about the objectives, results and outcomes of the project	Project dissemination and awareness	M25	MATE	MATE's community
Event		Project dissemination and awareness	M26	Flanders, Belgium	EUDRES Community and region + local network
Event "Citizen Science Workshop at UCLL Campus Diepenbeek"	Citizen Science Workshop at UCLL Campus Diepenbeek	Project dissemination and awareness	M26	UCLL	Ent-r-e-novators institutions and regions

Activity	Description	Reason why	Month	Place	Target
EDEN 2024 Research Workshop & PhD Schools	Live about "EDEN 2024 Research Workshop & PhD Schools' Masterclass în Timișoara"	Project dissemination and awareness	M26	UPT	Ent-r-e-novators institutions and regions
DEN 2024 Research Workshop & PhD Schools' Masterclass în Timișoara	DEN 2024 Research Workshop & PhD Schools' Masterclass în Timișoara	Project dissemination and awareness	M25	UPT	Ent-r-e-novators institutions and regions
Event: Presentation on the Workshop citizen science FULDA	workshop CS with presentation of diverse stakeholders & presentation of results WP5	Project dissemination and awareness	M26	Fulda, Germany	EUDRES Community and region + local network
Event: "Workshop Open Education & Science Practices 2025"	"Workshop Open Education & Science Practices 2025"	Project dissemination and awareness	M26	Hybrid	Ent-r-e-novators institutions and regions
Event: Digital skills workshop in artificial intelligence and community – DigiSkills 2024	Digital skills workshop in artificial intelligence and community – DigiSkills 2024	Project dissemination and awareness	M26	Hybrid	
Workshop CS & Skill Mapping game at SC event at Fulda	Workshop CS & Skill Mapping game at SC event at Fulda, November 22nd 2024	Project dissemination and awareness	M26	Fulda, Germany	FULDA's Community
Event: International Week STPUAS	workshop CS, presenting results WP5 & testing the developed games (maturity model)	Project dissemination and awareness	M26	STPUAS	EUDRES Community and region + local network
Workshop CS skill mapping game at International Week at STPUAS,	Workshop CS skill mapping game at Int'l week at STPUAS, November 27th 2024	Project dissemination and awareness	M26	STPUAS	EUDRES Community and region + local network
Webinar LearningPlanetInstitute & ECSA	Presentation of Entrenovators, WP5 results citizen and stakeholder engagement	Project dissemination and awareness	M27	UCLL	ECSA & Learning planet institute
Use of WP5 results in class	Muki Haklay (ECSA) presented and tested the maturity model framework in his classes at University College London	Project dissemination and awareness	M28	UCLL / ECSA	Students University College London
Event: "Open Science & Education Workshop"	workshop CS with presentation of diverse stakeholders & presentation of results WP5	Project dissemination and awareness	M29	Flanders, Belgium	EUDRES Community and region + local network
Event: Human Resources International workshop "From Scholars to Leaders: Strengthening Leadership and HR Management Skills in Academia"	Human Resources International workshop "From Scholars to Leaders: Strengthening Leadership and HR Management Skills in Academia"	Project dissemination and awareness	M30	VIA	Entrenovators institutions
Event: EXPER final Conference	Ent-r-e-novators presentation at the EXPER Conference	Project dissemination and awareness	M30	Hybrid Canarias	Exper institutions and scientific's
Event: Open education & science practices day UPT 2025	Presentation of WP5 results (online)	Project dissemination and awareness	M30	Timisoara	EUDRES' scientific's community

Activity	Description	Reason why	Month	Place	Target
Presentation at Open Education & Science Day at UPT	Presentation at Open Education & Science Day at UPT (hybrid), March 13th 2025	Project dissemination and awareness	M30	UPT	UPT's Community
Doctoral students from Vidzemes University of Applied Sciences learn about the new doctoral model and discuss the concept of open science	"Doctoral students from Vidzemes University of Applied Sciences learn about the new doctoral model and discuss the concept of open science"	Project dissemination and awareness	M30	ViA	ViA's community
Presentation - 2025 MCAA Annual Conference and General Assembly	Presentation about the project during the Marie Curie Alumni Association - MCAA workshop,	Project dissemination and awareness	M30	UCLL	Entrenovators institutions
Presentation about the Entrenovators project at the "Log's_Day Conference"	Conference for students, researchers and company professionals. One presentation about the Entrenovators project. Bilingual Event.	Project dissemination and awareness	M31	MATE	MATE community
Workshop CS, test scavenger hunt and stairs game at UCLL	Workshop CS, test scavenger hunt and stairs game at UCLL, May 5th, 2025 (10 teachers/researchers participated, Dutch, live)	Project dissemination and awareness	M32	UCLL	UPT's and scientific's Communities
Presentation of WP5 results at KULeuven Open Science Day	Presentation of WP5 results at KULeuven Open Science Day	Project dissemination and awareness	M32	KULeuven Belgium	KULeuven, and scientific's
Presentation - KU Leuven Open Science Day 2025	Presentation of WP5 results on Open Science Day at KULeuven, May 6th, 2025,	Project dissemination and awareness	M32	Irish College	Researchers (PhD students, postdocs, professors), KU Leuven and Association and external institutions
Science Policy Conference	Final Conference "Science Policy Conference Projeto E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-Novators"	Project dissemination and awareness	M32	Polytechnic University of Portalegre -Hybrid	Entrenovators institutions and regions
Presentation in the Conference for Advancing the Participatory Sciences (CAPS) 2025, Portland	workshop during the CAPS in the United States, for PhD students who want to integrate citizen science into their research proposals (9 participants)	Project dissemination and awareness	M32	Portland/United States	Scientific's community
Presentation at UCLouvain summer school	The activity was shared with colleagues at UCLouvain for the upcoming summer school	Project dissemination and awareness	M33	Louvain-la-Neuve	PhD students, postdocs, and researchers interested in Citizen Science
Staff Day	Annual staff event at ViA focusing on leadership skills and team building in	Project dissemination and awareness	M35	In Person ViA	ViA Staff

Activity	Description	Reason why	Month	Place	Target
	preparation for the new academic year.				
CS workshop & training	CS workshop & training for the WP5 materials for Scivil research team	Project dissemination and awareness	M36	Scivil, Belgium	Scivil research team
Event "Leaders of Future"	Starting event for cooperative projects between students, educators and companies.	Project dissemination and awareness	M36	MATE	MATE's and scientific's Communities
International Workshop on Citizen Science		Project dissemination and awareness	M36	In Person	Entrenovators institutions IPS Staff
International Workshop on Open Science, Open Education		Project dissemination and awareness	M36	In Person	Entrenovators institutions IPS Staff
WPs results poster presentation	Poster with the WPS results at the EUDRES Summit 2025	Project dissemination and awareness	M36	IPS	Entrenovators institutions and regions
European Researchers Night 2025 UPT	Project booth at European Researchers Night 2025	Project dissemination and awareness	M36	UPT	Entrenovators region
European Researchers Night 2025 MATE	Project booth at European Researchers Night 2025	Project dissemination and awareness	M36	MATE	Entrenovators region
European Researchers Night 2025 STPUAS	Project booth at European researchers night 2025	Project dissemination and awareness	M36	STPUAS	Entrenovators region
European researchers night 2025 ViA	Project booth at European researchers night 2025	Project dissemination and awareness	M36	ViA	Entrenovators region
European researchers night 2025 IPS	Project booth at European researchers night 2025	Project dissemination and awareness	M36	IPS	Entrenovators region
E³UDRES² – Ent-r-e-novators PhD Summer School 2025 – Open Practices in Higher Education	E³UDRES² – Ent-r-e-novators PhD Summer School 2025 – Open Practices in Higher Education	Project dissemination and awareness	M36	UPT	Entrenovators institutions and regions
The results and application of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project in the MATE Master's program in Supply Chain Management	Presentation about the objectives, results and outcomes of the project	Project dissemination and awareness		MATE	MATE's and scientific's Communities

2.2.3 Communication leads

Owned and earned media and shared activities

During the second reporting period, communication activities were almost evenly divided between channels managed directly by the project and those hosted by external partners. This balance highlights the project's increasing visibility and the strong capacity of external actors to amplify its dissemination. Across the 36 months, the overall trend confirms a strategic shift: while project-owned channels remained central, earned media and shared interactions gained greater weight, extending the reach of Ent-r-e-novators to wider and more diverse audiences.

In practice, activities are grouped into three categories of channels:

- **Owned Media**

Content produced and published directly through the project's channel (51% in the second period, 614 activities), which depended on and was controlled by WP1 of the Ent-r-e-novators. The project activity impacts the earned media results.

- **Earned Media**

- Coverage and dissemination through institutional partners, cluster projects and external organisations (49%, 371 activities) channels - that are not under the project's control

- **Shared Media**

Interactions with the project's social media content, amounting to 6943 likes, shares, comments and clicks.

Figure 16 compares the evolution of owned and earned media across the reporting period, showing clearly the scale of growth between the first and second reporting periods. Owned Media rose from 116 to 614 actions, while Earned Media grew from 62 to 371. This indicates a gradual shift from reliance on internal channels to a more balanced and diversified presence, reflecting the project's transition towards a collaborative communication model where results were amplified by external actors as well. Owned Media maintained a steady predominance, reflecting the systematic use of project-managed channels such as the website, newsletters and official social media. Earned Media, by contrast, displayed more irregular peaks, often associated with high-impact events. This was particularly visible in March and May 2025, when the Open Education & Science Practices Workshop and the Science & Policy Conference generated extensive coverage. Towards the end of the project, following the main conference, the volume of Earned Media naturally declined as external coverage slowed.

Figure 15 - Comparative evolution of media type usage

Shared Media also played a role in reinforcing dissemination. These interactions show that audiences did not simply receive information passively, but actively engaged with it, extending the circulation of content beyond the project's direct control. Posts were liked, commented on and re-shared across professional and civic communities, multiplying visibility and embedding the project's messages in wider conversations.

Figure 16 shows the main sources of Earned Media. Within Earned Media, Ent-r-e-novators institutions were by far the main drivers, accounting for more than two-thirds of all external dissemination. This demonstrates their active commitment to promoting project outcomes within their own communities and ensuring visibility in academic and regional contexts. Cluster projects also made a notable contribution, showing how synergies within the Horizon Europe call helped amplify results and extend reach beyond the immediate consortium. Coverage in the news media, together with posts from external institutions, further expanded the project's visibility to civic, regional and policy-oriented spheres. Even the smaller contributions, such as those from the E³UDRES² alliance and individual contributors, highlight the diversity of actors engaged and confirm that communication resonated across different levels of the European higher education ecosystem.

Figure 16 - Communication main Earned Media

Together, the three types of media complemented each other and reinforced the project's overall strategy. Owned Media guaranteed stability and consistency, Earned Media amplified visibility at key moments, and Shared Media provided an important role in engagement and resonance within wider communities. This interplay was essential to ensure that communication and dissemination not only delivered outputs but also generated lasting impact.

3. Exploitation Plan

3.1 Exploitative activities

As mentioned at the executive summary, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project is a collaborative endeavour aimed at refining a comprehensive joint research and innovation strategy, alongside a unified agenda. The overarching ambition is to catalyse the transformation of E³UDRES² into a distinguished European multi-institutional Research and Innovation Hub specialising in Smart and Sustainable Regions. With this propose several project results were produced, some of which have the potential to be exploited. As this project is a CSA without the objective of developing any product, methodology or other technological or scientific results, the way of dealing with the results and their exploitation is very specific to the topics covered in this project.

There are 5 key Exploitation Activities (EA) specified as follow:

1. **KER1: Network collaboration and sharing system (WP3):** A network collaboration and sharing system will be developed to harmonise the relative strengths and weaknesses of partners, reduce redundancies, and exploit synergies. Building on WP3 results (researcher survey, interactive mapping, transactional cost analysis, and synergy identification), the system goes beyond a simple database by integrating governance models, cost–benefit evaluation, and digital tools (ARENA platform). This approach enables a multiplicative increase of RD&I capacities across E³UDRES² partners and their stakeholders, providing transparent access to infrastructures, supporting policy alignment, and fostering regional and industry collaboration.
2. **KER2: Package of training activities on OS/OI/OE (WP4):** Training activities on OS/OI/OE based on workshops and summer schools for providing OS/OI/OE skills and competences.
3. **KER3: MOOC courses on OS/OI/OE (WP4):** The MOOC course for providing OS/OI/OE skills and competences. The MOOC course is available on the ARENA platform of the E²URES³ alliance.
4. **KER4: Maturity model for acquiring the engagement skills in Citizen Science (WP5):** The maturity model innovatively integrates citizen science engagement into researchers' career development by aligning competencies with the EURAXESS profiles.
5. **KER5: Package of training activities on Citizen Science (WP5):** Training activities on Citizen Science based on workshops and I - Living labs for Early Engagement and I - Living labs for engagement ambassadors.

3.2 E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Key Exploitable Results (KER) Analysis

KER Summary

The KER analysis is used to detail the responsibilities within the consortium for the implementation of the exploitative activities. All partners of the consortium contributed to the realization of the Exploitation Plan. In addition to this joint responsibility, individual partners are responsible for steering and managing milestones, this will be seen under each KER individual analysis action plan sub-sections.

All project consortium partners are interested in exploiting all KERs.

Next section analyses each E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Key Exploitable Results.

KER Analysis

This section describes and analyses each E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators exploitable result. To do so, it first does a characterization, then explains who is involved in the exploitation to then move into what are the risks that they might face and finally, takes into account the information in the previous sub-sections to develop the action plan that will be needed to bring the product to market.

3.2.1. KER1: Network collaboration and sharing system

Exploitable results characterization

This section's aim is to provide specific detail about the product's characteristics and how it is intended to be exploited. To do so it describes (1) the product/result, (2) the market in which it will compete and (3) the key things that the partnership will need to take into account to exploit the product.

The product

This KER will deliver a network collaboration and sharing system that will integrate research infrastructures across the E³UDRES² alliance. It will build on several WP3 outcomes:

- a large-scale researcher survey that will confirm strong demand for infrastructure sharing;
- interactive mapping of external RD&I resources, which will provide transparent and visual access for stakeholders;
- a transactional cost evaluation model that will support efficient and fair use of external infrastructures;
- identification of synergy key points and redundancies, which will enable smart allocation of capacities;
- integration with the ARENA digital platform for GDPR-compliant and user-friendly access.

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The system will go beyond traditional sharing initiatives by combining policy, governance, and cost–benefit perspectives. It will enable researchers to expand their participation in R&I projects, foster cross-institutional collaboration, and increase the number of contracts and partnerships at both regional and transnational levels.

The market

The market for this KER is the academic field and R&I ecosystems in the regions where the alliance universities are located.

Institutions in the region with infrastructures that can serve the research activities of E³UDRES² universities will be invited to include their infrastructures in the network sharing system, through the establishment of collaboration protocols, enabling increasing the research capabilities of alliance researchers enabling increasing the research capabilities of the alliance researchers for the development of new projects or research contracts.

The system will also address the needs identified by the WP3 researcher survey, where more than 75% of respondents expressed willingness to participate in infrastructure sharing. It will provide value not only to researchers but also to institutional leaders, regional policymakers, and industry partners who will benefit from transparent and efficient access to infrastructures.

There are several similar network sharing systems, some belonging to other European university alliances (e.g. RIs-UNITE!). This is an interesting market for the exploration of results, as it is possible to interconnect these different networks and thus expand contacts between researchers in the internal alliance and stakeholders from other European regions and other universities, as well as access to other infrastructure, promoting the increase of the research capabilities of the alliance researchers for the development of new projects or research contracts.

The Partnership

The current consortium of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project is capable to develop the sharing network bringing it to respective market. In the first phase, that is, considering the internal infrastructures. However, to extend to external infrastructures, other institutions, regional stakeholders and other networks it is necessary to create new partnerships and establish collaboration and exploitation agreements.

Exploitation Agreements

All the 6 partners of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project are going to benefit from this KER, all of them contributed to its development. As such, the partners reached the following agreements.

- All partners will collaborate in the development of the sharing network.

- Each partner will ensure the involvement and commitment of their institution's leadership in the development, maintenance and sustainability of the network.
- Each partner will be responsible for involving stakeholders in their region in participating in the sharing network.
- All partners accept that other partners can use the network to promote their research and development activities.
- Any partner wishing to change, develop or update the network must contact MATE, as responsible for its design in this project, and UPT as responsible for the development of the ARENA platform to plan and coordinate these activities, or others designated by the E³UDRES² alliance after the completion of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project.
- Partners will not share the information with other organizations outside the consortium that is not agreed that can be shared.

If the consortium decides a more comprehensive and detailed collaboration agreement should be drawn up and signed between the partners to regulate the exploitation of this KER, especially taking into account the use of the ARENA platform as the basis for the implementation of this sharing network and the way in which it will be developed within the alliance and the respective partners responsible for this.

Risks and controversies

To exploit this result, the involved partners need to consider a series of risks and controversies. As such, this section takes them into account. In short, they are: (1) partnership, (2) technological, (3) market, (4) legal, (5) financial/management and (6) environmental. The following risk priority map classifies these risks according to the priority that partners need to act to overcome the challenges they bring (see Annex). They are afterwards further developed.

Figure 17 - KER1, Priority Map

The priority map shows that in order to exploit the result, all the potential risks will need to be under control. This does not mean that as the partners decide to exploit the results the risks go from control to action. Next sub-section explains why the risks need to be under control.

Control Factors

Partnership: The biggest risk in relation to partnership is disagreement over ownership rules. Another important risk is the possible weak adherence of external institutions, to collaborate with our sharing network.

The first risk can be mitigated by preparing a consortium agreement, signed by all partners, where the role of each one must be well defined and clearly defined. There should be a periodic analysis of the protocol's suitability with the evolution of the network and, if necessary, its revision. The second risk can be mitigated and controlled by doing the network with just a few other external institutions or without them and promote the network to motivate more and more external entities to participate.

Technological: The greatest technological risk is related to the technological solution that will have to robustly guarantee Data Security and Protection, and security against cyber-attacks and unauthorized access to confidential data. Another important risk is related to the possible inefficient operation and inadequate maintenance of the server that host the platform of the sharing network.

The first risk can be controlled and mitigated by a robust network to address this risk, it must be continuously monitored for this risk, and the maintenance team must be competent and well prepared to intervene quickly and effectively if the risk materializes. The second risk can be

controlled and mitigated by analysing who among the E³UDRES² alliance partners will have the best solution for hosting the network, even if it is only temporarily.

Market: Appearance of other networks with more effective and accessible technological solutions making this solution obsolete. Another important risk is that there may be different interests among partners in how to exploit the sharing network.

The first risk can be controlled by analysing the advantages of other networks and implement them in this network. To address the second one, it is suggested to create a working group for the development, maintenance and promotion of the network involving all partners with close ties to the leadership of the respective universities.

Legal: the most important risk is related with the compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly regarding data privacy and intellectual property, poses significant challenges. The second risk is risk of not complying with the internal regulations of each alliance university and external stakeholders.

To address the first risk, it is necessary that the development group and the maintenance group must analyse in detail all legal requirements in all countries involved, ensuring that all are complied with, on an ongoing basis. To control and mitigated the second risks is it necessary that the development group and the maintenance group analyses in detail all internal regulations of all partner universities and all external stakeholders, ensuring that they are all complied with, on an ongoing basis.

Financial and management: the most important risk is related with the ability to ensure effectively managing the functioning of the network, when it is necessary to be in convergence with the management of the different partners and with their various management substructures. Another important risk is to ensure enough resources (human and/or financial) to secure the next step toward exploitation and to maintain that exploitation.

To control this first risk, it is necessary to establish a centralised risk management team composed of representatives from each institution. This team will oversee the development and implementation of risk management policies, ensuring consistency across all partners. To address the second risk it is necessary to try to find external financing ((national, European and private funding) to guarantee the resources to maintain and update the sharing network platform.

Environmental regulations: The most important risk is related to data protection and GDPR compliance in cross-border sharing of infrastructure information. Another important risk is the lack

of harmonised regulatory and ethical standards across partner countries, which may cause delays in approvals and conflicts with national rules.

The first risk can be mitigated by introducing GDPR-compliant data management protocols, anonymisation where possible, and regular legal audits to ensure ongoing compliance. The second risk can be controlled and mitigated by developing standardised cooperation agreements and common ethical frameworks across the alliance, while also aligning sustainability measures with EU Green Deal objectives.

Action Plan

The action plan outlines the key milestones that are going to be needed to exploit the sharing network. As such, considering the KER analysis, an action plan is presented that will have to be followed so that this result can be exploited.

Table 3 - KER1, Action Plan

#	Task	Deadline
1	Develop and sign a collaboration agreement between the partners, including the new 3 new partners of the E ³ UDRES ² alliance.	6 months after the project.
2	Create the governance structure and receptive working groups of the sharing network.	6 months after the project.
3	Complete the network deployment and perform operational and robustness tests on the ARENA platform. First version created and tested.	months after the project.
4	Seek partnerships with external institutions, other networks and other alliances of European universities	12 months after the project.
6	Monitor, update and improve network sharing.	Every 6 months
7	Capture new partners, disseminate and promote internally and externally.	Continuously

3.2.2. KER2: Package of training activities on OS/OI/OE

Exploitable results characterization

This section's aim is to provide specific detail about the product's characteristics and how it is intended to be exploited. To do so it describes (1) the product/result, (2) the market in which it will compete and (3) the key things that the partnership will need to take into account to exploit the product.

This section characterises the structured package of pilot training activities—workshops, webinars, and a summer school—that focus on implementing Open Practices (Open Education, Open Access, Open Science, and Open Innovation). These activities were developed and delivered as

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part of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, aiming to move beyond theoretical concepts and illustrate the practical application of open practices in real-world university environments and research projects.

The product

The Exploitable Result (KER) is the comprehensive, packaged training programme encompassing various formats designed to foster knowledge sharing and skill development in Open Practices.

The pilot actions delivered include:

1. **Workshops and Seminars:** Multiple international workshops and seminars focusing on Open Education, Open Science, and Open Access were held in a hybrid or in-person format by various partners, including UPT, STPUAS, UCLL, IPS, ViA. These events established a platform for professionals, academics, and researchers, and early stage researchers to share knowledge and expertise. These products include: the methodology for planning, delivering and evaluating the workshops, the evaluation survey, methods of engagement. All of them were produced during the lifetime of the project, made available to all partners and published within the consortium.
 - **Content Focus:** Challenges in Open Science and Education, practical application of OERs, impact of emerging technologies (AI, VR, Blockchain), research data management, and institutional strategies for integrating Open Practices.
 - **Outcomes:** These sessions deliver valuable insights into motivators and barriers for adoption of open practices, such as concerns over defining clear content boundaries, intellectual property rights, and financial limitations for publishing open access.
 - **Feedback:** Feedback was overwhelmingly positive, with UPT workshops receiving over 90% positive ratings and the IPS workshop achieving high satisfaction, inspiring more than 50% of participants to use open practices in their teaching or research, as shown on the later stage follow up survey.
2. **Webinars:** Online sessions focused on specific topics related to Open Access and Open Science, such as "Open statistical data" and "Open science tools",
 - **Content Focus:** Enhancing skills regarding open access, open science, and the use and sharing of open data. Introduction to a range of tools supporting the entire research lifecycle within the framework of Open Science.
 - **Outcomes:** Participants gained new ideas and knowledge, with all respondents from the "Open statistical data" webinar stating they would likely use open statistical data in their daily activities.

3. **Summer School (Intensive Programme):** The E³UDRES² – Ent-r-e-novators PhD Summer School 2025 focused on **"Open Practices in Higher Education"** over five days.
- **Content Focus:** Foundational concepts of Open Education, Open Science, Open Access, and Open Innovation, combining theoretical lectures with practical, hands-on activities.
 - **Audience/Scope:** It attracted over 70 international early stage researchers in person and 400 online participants.
 - **Recognition:** Participants were awarded official participation certificates recognised for **2 ECTS credits**, along with 70 Certificates of Participation for on-site attendees and 400 online Open Badges.
 - **Outcomes:** This intensive training programme produced over XXX presentations, all live sessions were recorded by resulting xxx videos, xxx interactive activities, and a final quiz. All of them are available in the E³UDRES² Arena Learning Hub, a digital platform developed by the E³UDRES² Alliance at arena.eudres.eu/learning.
 - **Overall Recognition:** Participants in various events received digital Open Badges (e.g., Open Practices Workshop Participant Open Badge, Open Practices Webinar Open Badges) or traditional Certificates of Participation.

The Market

The market for this KER includes various academic and research groups across Europe and internationally:

- **Target Audience:** Researchers (early-stage and senior), students (Master's and PhD students), educators, professors, research managers, and other professionals.
- **Potential Market:** Other alliances of European universities, universities, research centers, and institutions seeking to integrate modern, collaborative, and future-oriented open practices into higher education and research. This includes institutions responding to challenges posed by emerging technologies like AI, VR, and Blockchain towards the integration of open practices.

The Partnership

The training activities were organised and delivered by partners within the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project consortium.

- **Key Developers/Organizers:** Politehnica University of Timișoara (UPT), St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS), Hungarian University of Agricultural and Life

Sciences (MATE), Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (ViA), UCLL, and the Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS).

- **Capacity:** The partnership includes international experts from multiple countries (e.g., Romania, Portugal, Italy, Belgium, Latvia, Hungary, the Netherlands, and Austria).
- **Exploitation:** The partnership seeks to promote collaboration and establish educational networks and aims to build on current success by expanding future editions and deepening partnerships with academic and industry experts within the E³UDRES² Alliance.
- **Nature of Future Partnerships:** Partnerships formed to exploit these results could be simple (direct use of materials with initial support) or more complex (involving consortium experts to adapt materials to new contexts or specificities).

Exploitation Agreements

Given that the partners of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project contributed to the development and piloting of these training actions, they have reached the following agreements based on the consortium model:

- **Dissemination Collaboration:** All partners will collaborate in finding third parties interested in the training materials, focusing on their respective country and region.
- **Derivative Use:** Each partner retains the right to exploit, create derivative material, and share results without needing permission from the other partners, provided a **reference to the Ent-r-e-novators project is explicitly included**.
- **Internal Sharing:** When additional materials (e.g., guides, tutorials, in-depth workshops) based on these pilot activities are developed by a consortium partner, these new results will be shared within the consortium.
- **Formal Regulation:** If the consortium deems it necessary, a more comprehensive and detailed collaboration agreement should be drawn up and signed between the partners to formally regulate the exploitation of this KER.

Risks and controversies

In order to exploit this result, the training program, the involved partners need to consider a series of risks and controversies. As such, this section takes them into account. In short, they are: (1) partnership, (2) technological, (3) market, (4) legal, (5) financial/management and (6) environmental. The following risk priority map classifies these risks according to the priority that partners need to act to overcome the challenges they bring (see Annex). They are further developed afterwards.

Figure 18 - KER2, Priority Map

The priority map shows that in order to exploit the result, all the potential risks will need to be under control. This does not mean that as the partners decide to exploit the results the risks go from control to action. Next sub-section explains why the risks need to be under control.

Control Factors

Partnership: The biggest risk in relation to partnership is the possibility of a partner developing derivative materials based on the training materials without making reference to the original materials or the Ent-r-e-novators project. Another risk might be that a partner developing additional materials based on the original training pack without informing the other partners of the consortium. This risk can be mitigated through the following procedure: partners using the projects' deliverables always mention the source of the deliverable. Also, when developing new materials these should be shared within the consortium with all partners involved.

Technological: As several of these training events were hybrid or online, a technological risk relies on the videoconference platform used. When developing new events or resources, partners must carefully select platforms that ensure **GDPR compliance**, utilize **encryption**, and implement strong legal safeguards. Organizing more in-depth events, including hands-on workshops, and developing practical guides or tutorials on specific tools can serve as enduring resources and help standardise technological approaches.

Market: Since the training materials (e.g., presentations, recordings, outcomes from interactive sessions) are available in an open framework, a major risk is that alliances of universities, universities, and European research centres may use the materials without contacting the

developing partners. Furthermore, potential users might not understand the importance of integrating open practices into their daily activities or of the use of the training materials for their early stage researchers.

The first risk can be mitigated through that the E³UDRES² Alliance researchers should actively approach other institutions to promote their work and explain the advantages of applying the materials. The importance and benefits of using the training materials should be continually promoted. Considering the creation of hands-on, professional training materials and the existing on the materials in the Arena Learning Hub, an online tool, it could ensure correct and controlled use. The second risk can be controlled by the promotion of the importance and advantages of using the training materials, by the E³UDRES² alliance researchers involved in these training materials.

Legal: The most important risk is related to compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly concerning GDPR compliance and data sharing. Limitations may arise during the use of the training materials by third parties, especially concerning the balance of intellectual property rights with open collaboration. To address this risk it is necessary that the researchers involved in exploiting the materials analyse in detail the legal requirements of each country, together with third parties, for each case of application of the materials, ensuring that all are complied with. When engaging in open innovation, especially with confidential business data, careful platform selection and legal safeguards are crucial.

Financial and management: Risks include the lack of approval from the leadership of each partner institution regarding establishing exploitation agreements with third parties. A second risk is the possible lack of interest of any partner in making an effort to ensure the continuous exploration and maintenance of the training materials, such as updating content with open practices on AI or other emergent technologies. To control the first risk, it is necessary that the researchers at each institution involved in open practices activities, more specifically exploiting the materials, should inform their institution's leadership about the importance of establishing an agreement with third parties to explore the training materials.

Partners interested in continuing to exploit this result must make an additional, joint effort to keep the training materials actively exploited, perhaps by expanding future editions and deepening partnerships.

Environmental regulations: There are no identified risks.

Action Plan

The action plan outlines the key milestones that are going to be needed to exploit the training materials (workshops, seminars, webinars, summer school). As such, taking into account the KER analysis, an action plan is presented that will have to be followed so that this result can be exploited. Some of the results from this KER are already planned to be further developed – the International Workshop on Open Practices is planned to be organised again in March 2026, The Summer school is planned to be organised during 22-26 May 2026, trainers and participants are already in the process of being attracted.

Table 4 - KER2, Action Plan

#	Task	Deadline
1	Develop and sign a collaboration agreement between the partners, including the new 3 new partners of the E³UDRES² alliance.	6 months after the project.
2	Identify a set of researchers per E³UDRES² alliance institution interested in using, adapting, and exploiting the training materials (workshops, webinars, summer school content), using the ARENA digital platform.	6 months after the project.
3	Frequently update the set of researchers from the previous item.	Every 6 months
4	Start promoting the training materials with other European university alliances, universities and research centres by the E³UDRES² alliance researchers.	9 months after the project.
5	As the E³UDRES² Alliance is a member of COARA and European Open Science Cloud and through it promote the training materials.	9 months after the project.
6	Periodic monitoring of the possible emergence of new training materials and training materials development by responsible team, who will be defined in the collaboration agreement.	Every 6 months.
7	Plan the expansion of future editions of the summer school and workshops, deepening partnerships with academic and research experts from other Alliances	Every 6-12 months

3.2.3. KER3: MOOC courses on OS/OI/OE

Exploitable results characterization

This section characterises the four new online courses launched as part of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, focusing on the Foundations of Open Practices. These courses, which cover Open Education (OE), Open Access (OA), Open Science (OS), and Open Innovation (OI), are freely available to all students and staff across the E³UDRES² Alliance universities and also open to authors in the Arena Learning Hub.

The Product

The Foundations of Open Practices online programme is designed to be **open, free, and accessible for flexible participation**. It consists of four self-sustained, non-facilitated courses that learners can complete at their own pace and time.

The overall programme provides an in-depth introduction to the principles, practices, and applications of Open Education, Open Access, Open Science, and Open Innovation. Learners acquire skills in creating and utilising open resources, understand open licensing, and develop competencies for collaboration and innovation in open environments. The programme introduces participants to the principles, history, and applications of openness in education, research, science, the use of open data and FAIR data, and open innovation and information about citizen science, equipping them with essential skills for the digital age.

The four core courses are:

1. Licensing and Open Licensing

- **Focus:** Comprehensive understanding of licensing, concentrating on open licences within the context of intellectual property, digital content, and innovation. Learners will learn about different types of licences, legal frameworks, and how to apply open licences.
- **Highlights:** Understanding copyright and licensing principles, applying Creative Commons licenses, evaluating reusability of works, and gaining knowledge of open-source tools and practices.
- **Duration:** 5 hours of self-paced activities.
- **Creators:** Dr. Diana Andone and Dr. Vlad Mihaescu.

2. Open Education

- **Focus:** Discovering how openness transforms education, including creating and using Open Educational Resources (OERs), and exploring MOOCs, AI, and open pedagogies. Key topics include the history and philosophy of openness, the 5R framework (retain, reuse, revise, remix, redistribute), and the benefits and challenges of Open Educational Practices (OEP).
- **Outcome:** Learners will be able to create, modify, and utilise OER effectively, applying appropriate licensing, and aligning resources with pedagogical goals. Topics include Open Pedagogy, principles of participatory and learner-centered teaching, and co-creation of knowledge with students.

- **Highlights:** Applying the 5R framework to OERs, creating and sharing OERs with proper licensing, engaging in open pedagogies, and exploring MOOCs and AI in open education.
- **Duration:** 24 hours (1 ECTS) of self-paced learning.
- **Creators:** Dr. Diana Andone, Dr. Vlad Mihaescu, Dr. Andrei Ternauciuc, and Dr. Silvia Couvaneiro.

3. Open Access and Open Science

- **Focus:** Learning to publish, share, and manage research openly and responsibly while applying reproducibility and FAIR data principles. This includes different models of open access publishing, navigating the open access process, and applying open licenses in science and research.
- **Topics:** Principles of transparency and reproducibility, open methodologies, FAIR and open peer review, media literacy, tools and platforms supporting open science, and navigating predatory journals.
- **Highlights:** Understanding open access publishing models, applying open licenses to publications, data, and code, implementing transparency and reproducibility, and drafting an Open Science implementation plan.
- **Duration:** 15 hours of online learning activities.
- **Creators:** Dr. Silviu Vert, Dr. Diana Andone, Dr. Agnese Dāvidsone, Dr. Tassilo Pellegrini, Dr. Radu VasIU.

4. Open Innovation

- **Focus:** Introducing the principles of open innovation and collaboration in education, research, and entrepreneurship. This course explores ecosystems of innovation, problem-solving, and future trends in collaborative practices.
- **Topics:** Principles of open innovation, collaborative models, and networking in open environments. It includes knowledge of the innovation landscape, such as startup culture, incubators, accelerators, and industry trends, as well as case studies.
- **Highlights:** Understanding the principles and models of open innovation, exploring collaboration and networking, analysing case studies and challenges, and developing strategies for applying open innovation practices.
- **Duration:** To be completed at your own pace.
- **Creator:** Ann Reulens, Tassilo Pelegrini, Ilse Gilisen, Silvia Fierascu.

- **Recognition:** Each course awards learners a **certificate of completion**. Learners who successfully complete all four courses will receive the **Foundations of Open Practices Certificate**, which recognises their knowledge, competencies, and commitment to openness, collaboration, and innovation.

The Market

The courses are primarily directed at **every early stage researchers, researchers, research managers, students, academics and staff member of the E³UDRES² Alliance**. By engaging with these courses, learners join a wider international movement that is shaping the future of higher education and research.

The Partnership

The courses were launched as part of the **E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project**. They were developed by a consortium of creators and are accessible to the staff and students of the **E³UDRES² Alliance** and area available in the Arena Learning Hub, a digital platform based on Moodle, where all members of the Alliance can login through Edugain.

Exploitation Agreements

Given that the partners of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project contributed to the development of these MOOC style courses and they are free and open to all, all partners have interests in using them. They have reached the following agreements based on the consortium model:

- **Dissemination Collaboration:** All partners will collaborate in finding third parties interested in the MOOC courses, focusing on their respective country and region.
- **Derivative Use:** Each partner retains the right to exploit, create derivative material, and share results without needing permission from the other partners, provided a **reference to the Ent-r-e-novators project is explicitly included**.
- **Internal Sharing:** When additional materials results (i.e., the Foundations of Open Practices courses) based on these courses are developed by a consortium partner, these new results will be shared within the consortium.
- **Formal Regulation:** If the consortium deems it necessary, a more comprehensive and detailed collaboration agreement should be drawn up and signed between the partners to formally regulate the exploitation of this KER.

Risks and controversies

In order to exploit this result, the MOOCs courses, the involved partners need to consider a series of risks and controversies. As such, this section takes them into account. In short, they are: (1) partnership, (2) technological, (3) market, (4) legal, (5) financial/management and (6) environmental. The following risk priority map classifies these risks according to the priority that partners need to act to overcome the challenges they bring (see Annex). They are afterwards further developed.

Figure 19 - KER3, Priority Map

The priority map shows that in order to exploit the result, all the potential risks will need to be under control. This does not mean that as the partners decide to exploit the results the risks go from control to action. Next sub-section explains why the risks need to be under control.

Control Factors

Partnership: The biggest risk in relation to partnership is the possibility of a partner developing derivative materials based on the MOOCs without making reference to the original materials or the Ent-r-e-novators project. Another risk might be that a partner developing additional materials based on the original Courses without informing the other partners of the consortium. This risk can be mitigated through the following procedure: partners using the projects' deliverables always mention the source of the deliverable. Also, when developing new educational resources, these should be shared within the consortium with all partners involved.

Technological: As all of the MOOCs Courses are online, a technological risk relies on the support of the Arena Learning Hub, the digital platform used. The courses are available and online as long as the platform is alive and running, which depends on the E³UDRES² Alliance funding and support.

This risk is mitigated by the agreement available, for the next 3 years the courses will be supported technically by the alliance digital support team.

Market: Since the training materials (courses and resources) are available as open data and are freely available, alliances of universities, universities, and European research centres may use the materials without contacting the developing partners. A second risk is that potential users outside the E³UDRES² Alliance might not understand the importance of using the training materials or the value of the resulting Foundations of Open Practices Badge.

Exploring the possibility of multiply the courses on other platforms, of the institutions or professional MOOCs platforms, could help ensure correct and controlled use of the materials. E³UDRES² Alliance researchers should actively approach other institutions to promote their work and explain the advantages of counting on the project researchers' experience in applying the materials. The importance and benefits of using the educational resources should be continually promoted by the involved E³UDRES² Alliance researchers.

Legal: The most important risk is related to compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly concerning GDPR compliance and data sharing. Limitations may arise during the use of the courses by third parties, especially concerning the balance of intellectual property rights with open collaboration. To address this risk it is necessary that the researchers involved in accessing and re-sharing the educational resources and materials analyse in detail the legal requirements of each country, together with third parties, for each case of application of the materials. ensuring that all are complied with.

Financial and management: Risks include the lack of approval from the leadership of each partner institution regarding establishing exploitation agreements with third parties. A second risk is the possible lack of interest of any partner in making an effort to ensure the continuous exploration and maintenance of the MOOCs, such as updating content with open practices and new EU perspectives for Open science. To control the first risk, it is necessary that the researchers at each institution involved in open practices activities, more specifically exploiting the materials, should inform their institution's leadership about the importance of establishing an agreement with third parties to explore the courses.

Partners interested in continuing to exploit this result must make an additional, joint effort to keep the MOOCs actively exploited, perhaps by expanding future editions and deepening partnerships.

Environmental regulations: There are no identified risks.

Action Plan

The action plan outlines the key milestones that are going to be needed to exploit the MOOCs courses – 4 online, free and accessible to all courses, and the results as Open Badges. As such, taking into account the KER analysis, an action plan is presented that will have to be followed so that this result can be exploited.

The results from this KER are already planned to be further developed and sustained, the MOOCs courses are available and easy to access in the Alliance Learning Hub, including the 3 partners not part of this project. They are actively promoted by the E³UDRES² Alliance marketing and main management office as a demonstration on further microcredential development.

Table 5 - KER3, Action Plan

#	Task	Deadline
1	Develop and sign a collaboration agreement between the partners, including the new 3 new partners of the E ³ UDRES ² alliance.	6 months after the project.
2	Identify a set of researchers per E ³ UDRES ² alliance institution interested in using, adapting, and exploiting the MOOCs, using the ARENA digital platform.	6 months after the project.
3	Frequently update the set of researchers from the previous item.	Every 6 months
4	Start promoting the MOOCs with other European university alliances, universities and research centers by the E ³ UDRES ² alliance researchers.	9 months after the project.
5	As the E ³ UDRES ² Alliance is a member of COARA and European Open Science Cloud and through it promote the MOOCs, as well as by publishing results at conferences.	9 months after the project.
6	Periodic monitoring of the possible emergence of new training materials and training materials development by responsible team, who will be defined in the collaboration agreement.	Every 6 months.
7	Plan the expansion of future MOOCs by the Alliance, as models for Microcredentials.	6 months after the project.

3.2.4. KER4: Maturity model for acquiring the engagement skills in Citizen Science

Exploitable results characterisation

This section's aim is to provide specific detail about the product's characteristics and how it is intended to be exploited. To do so it describes (1) the product/result, (2) the market in which it will compete and (3) the key things that the partnership will need to take into account to exploit the product.

The product

The maturity model is a framework which was created throughout the Ent-r-e-novators project, based on (i) the 8 categories of essential engagement competencies for researchers, which were identified through a multi-phased approach ran by the six involved universities of applied sciences (rooted in the results of the Delphi study from Task 5.1. and (ii) the EURAXESS Researcher Profile Descriptors, which categorize researchers into First Stage Researcher (R1), Recognized Researcher (R2), Established Researcher (R3), and Leading Researcher (R4).

In our maturity model we mapped the 8 engagement competences to the four levels of expertise in Citizen Science (CS). With this tool, one can scale his/her engagement skills ranging from junior to senior citizen scientist for these 8 categories. It gives a clear view of which skills you already possess, and which still need more development. At an individual level, the maturity model can be used as a self-assessment tool for engagement skills, so researchers can identify their strengths, but also their needs for further training in CS skills.

Furthermore, the maturity model can also be used as an interesting exercise to do with a project team. As Citizen Science is meant to be transdisciplinary, everyone has their specific expertise. We don't expect one person to be an expert in all these skills. With the maturity model, team roles and strengths can be identified, as well as gaps that need to be filled by e.g. adding other project members with specific expertise to the team or planning targeted training for missing skills within the team.

The market

The market for this KER is essentially other alliances of European universities, universities, research centres, citizen science associations, (local) government institutions, NGOs, which need to develop activities related to citizen science. Workshops can be developed in which project teams can be trained on ideal team composition depending on available CS skills, using the maturity model. Derivatives or additional material can be developed, so the maturity model exercise can be used by all target groups on an independent basis.

The Partnership

The Maturity model was developed by the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project consortium, with its development led by UCLL. The consortium and especially UCLL have the capacity to apply the model in different contexts and conditions. However, it can also be adapted to specific and special conditions. The partnerships that may be formed to exploit this result will depend on what the third party intends. It could be a simple partnership, with direct use of the maturity model by the third party, with only initial support from one of the partners of the project consortium, or it could be a

more complex partnership with the involvement of experts from the consortium and the third party to adapt the maturity model to new contexts or specificities.

Exploitation Agreements

All the 6 partners of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project are going to benefit from this KER, all of them contributed in its development.

As such, the partners reached the following agreements.

- All partners will collaborate in finding third parties interested in the maturity model, with a greater focus on their country and region.
- Each partner will be able to exploit, make derivative material and share results without needing to ask permission from the other partners, as long as there is a reference to the maturity model and the Ent-r-e-novators project included.
- When additional materials based on the maturity model are developed by a partner, the results will be shared within the Consortium.

If the consortium decides, a more comprehensive and detailed collaboration agreement should be drawn up and signed between the partners to regulate the exploitation of this KER.

Risks and controversies

In order to exploit this result, the involved partners need to consider a series of risks and controversies. As such, this section takes them into account. In short, they are: (1) partnership, (2) technological, (3) market, (4) legal, (5) financial/management and (6) environmental. The following risk priority map classifies these risks according to the priority that partners need to act to overcome the challenges they bring (see Annex). They are afterwards further developed.

Figure 20 - KER4, Priority Map

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The priority map shows that in order to exploit the result, all the potential risks will need to be under control. This does not mean that as the partners decide to exploit the results the risks go from control to action. Next sub-section explains why the risks need to be under control.

Control Factors

Partnership: The biggest risk in relation to partnership is the possibility of a partner developing derivative materials based on the maturity model without making reference to the original model or the Ent-r-e-novators project. Another risk might be that a partner developing additional materials based on the original model without informing the other partners of the consortium. This risk can be mitigated through the following procedure: partners using the projects' deliverables always mention the source of the deliverable. Also, when developing new materials these should be shared within the consortium with all partners involved in WP5.

Technological: *There are no identified risks.*

Market: A major risk is that, since the maturity model is available in open data, open science, the alliances of universities, universities and European research centres will be able to use the maturity model developed without contacting us.

The second most important risk is related to the possibility of alliances of European universities, universities and research centres not understanding the importance of the use of the model for their citizen science activities.

The first risk can be mitigated through an approach by researchers from the E³UDRES² alliance to other institutions, to promote their work and explain the advantages to third parties of counting on the experience of these researchers in applying the maturity model, and also, by developing a (e.g. licenced) card game, the alliance has control over the correct use of the maturity model exercise. Information about the model and how to use it is open source, available online. The 'official' hands-on material can only be ordered via contacting the involved Ent-r-e-novators researchers (at UCLL).

The second risk can be controlled by the promotion of the importance and advantages of using the maturity model and how to use it, by the E³UDRES² alliance researchers involved in the model.

Legal: The most important risk is related with the compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly regarding data privacy and intellectual property, there may be some limitations during the use of the maturity model by some third parties.

To address this risk it is necessary that the researchers involved in exploiting the maturity model analyse in detail the legal requirements of each country, together with third parties, for each case of application of the model. ensuring that all are complied with.

Financial and management: The most important risks is related with the lack of approval from the leadership of each partner institution involved in the agreement with third parties.

The second most important risk is related to the possible lack of interest of any partner in making an effort to ensure the continuous exploration of the maturity model.

To control the first risk, it is necessary that the researchers at each institution involved in citizen science activities, more specifically exploiting the maturity model, should inform their institution's leadership about the importance of establishing an agreement with third parties to explore the model.

To control the second risk, partners interested in continuing to exploit this result must make an additional, joint effort to keep the maturity model actively exploited.

Environmental regulations: *There are no identified risks.*

Action Plan

The action plan outlines the key milestones that are going to be needed to exploit the maturity model. As such, taking into account the KER analysis, an action plan is presented that will have to be followed so that this result can be exploited.

Table 6 - KER4, Action Plan

#	Task	Deadline
1	Develop and sign a collaboration agreement between the partners, including the new 3 new partners of the E ³ UDRES ² alliance.	6 months after the project.
2	Identify a set of researchers per E ³ UDRES ² alliance institution interested in using and exploiting the maturity model, using the ARENA platform.	6 months after the project.
3	Frequently update the set of researchers from the previous item.	Every 6 months
4	Start promoting the maturity model with other European university alliances, universities and research centers by the E ³ UDRES ² alliance researchers.	6 months after the project.
5	Make the E ³ UDRES ² Alliance a member of European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and through it promote the maturity model.	9 months after the project.
6	Periodic monitoring of the possible emergence of new maturity models and model review by responsible team, who will be defined in the collaboration agreement.	Every 6 months.

3.2.5. KER5: Package of training activities on Citizen Science

Exploitable results characterization

This section's aim is to provide specific detail about the product's characteristics and how it is intended to be exploited. To do so it describes (1) the product/result, (2) the market in which it will compete and (3) the key things that the partnership will need to take into account to exploit the product.

The product

The Ent-r-e-novators Citizen Science toolkit consists of several tools, evolving throughout the Ent-r-e-novators project:

- **Powerpoint presentations** with basic information on citizen science were developed and shared within the partnership. In this way, partners were facilitated in drawing up the content of the workshops and trainings and it helped to standardize the way we 'tell the story'. Presentations can be tailored to country specific needs and examples of local citizen science projects can be added to make participants more familiar with what citizen science is and how it works.
- **Interactive games:** The games were developed in response to the need to transform the available resources into more accessible tools for researchers and stakeholders who will be involved in the Living Labs and CS projects. Aim of the first two games is to help researchers identify key citizen science principles and understand the different levels of engagement in citizen science. They provide a more general audience with an interactive way to deepen their understanding of citizen science and its main tasks and fundamental principles. The third game is more specifically aimed at university research staff and is mainly focused on identifying the skills necessary for ensuring citizen science at the level of a researcher – an individual, a research group or research organizations.
 - *Citizen Science scavenger hunt:* game to familiarize participants with the main principles of citizen science. The game consists of a PowerPoint with a fictional story about a scientist who organizes a citizen science project and a bingo card with 16 principles of citizen science. While going through the story, participants have to cross out the citizen science principle that they recognize in the story.
 - *Citizen Science stairs:* game to familiarize participants with the levels of engagement in citizen science projects and to raise awareness of different ways how citizens can be engaged. The game consists of a poster that illustrates the three levels of engagement in

citizen science projects and a set of cards with descriptions of 9 improvised citizen engagement situations, which have to be mapped on the levels or stairs from the poster.

- *Citizen Science skills inventory*: game-based group activity based on the Citizen Science maturity model and provides insight into knowledge and skills needed for researchers practicing citizen science projects and support research teams to identify skill gaps. It can be used in groups, or by individuals – giving them the opportunity to identify, assess, and reflect on their skills required for successful citizen engagement in research.

– Knowledge clips

Five knowledge clips were produced, where all information available was transformed into short, easily accessible videos:

1. Why citizen engagement
2. Recognizing citizen science (game 1)
3. Different levels of engagement (game 2)
4. Different engagement skills
5. Recognizing your engagement skills (game 3)

The market

The market for this KER is essentially other alliances of European universities, universities, research centres, citizen science associations, (local) government institutions, NGOs, who feel the need to familiarize employees, educators or researchers with what citizen science is and what its basic principles are. In order to use our materials on an independent basis, the materials have to be further developed and professionalized. Also, additional resources can be developed in order to use the games in an online training environment.

The Partnership

The training activities were developed by the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project consortium, with its development led by VIA and UCLL. The consortium, particularly UCLL, has the capacity to apply the materials in various contexts and conditions. However, they can also be adapted to specific conditions. The partnerships that may be formed to exploit these results will depend on what the third party intends. It could be a simple partnership, with direct use of the training materials by the third party, with only initial support from the project consortium, or it could be a more complex partnership with the involvement of experts from the consortium and the third party to adapt the materials to new contexts or specificities.

Exploitation Agreements

All six partners of the E3UDRES2 Ent-r-e-novators project are going to benefit from this KER, all of them contributed to its development.

As such, the partners reached the following agreements.

- All partners will collaborate in finding third parties interested in the training materials, with a greater focus on their country and region.
- Each partner will be able to exploit, make derivative material and share results without needing to ask permission from the other partners, as long as there is a reference to the Entr-e-novators project included.
- When additional materials based on the Entr-e-novators WP5 results are developed by a partner of the consortium, these results will be shared within the consortium.

If the consortium decides, a more comprehensive and detailed collaboration agreement should be drawn up and signed between the partners to regulate the exploitation of this KER.

Risks and controversies

In order to exploit this result, the involved partners need to consider a series of risks and controversies. As such, this section takes them into account. In short, they are: (1) partnership, (2) technological, (3) market, (4) legal, (5) financial/management and (6) environmental. The following risk priority map classifies these risks according to the priority that partners need to act to overcome the challenges they bring (see Annex). They are afterwards further developed.

Figure 21 - KER5, Priority Map

The priority map shows that in order to exploit the result, all the potential risks will need to be under control. This does not mean that as the partners decide to exploit the results the risks go from control to action. Next sub-section explains why the risks need to be under control.

Control Factors

Partnership: The biggest risk in relation to partnership is the possibility of a partner developing derivative materials based on the training materials without making reference to the original materials or the Ent-r-e-novators project. Another risk might be that a partner develops additional materials based on the original training pack without informing the other partners of the consortium. This risk can be mitigated through the following procedure: partners using the project's deliverables always mention the source of the deliverable. Also, when developing new materials, these should be shared within the consortium with all partners involved.

Technological: *There are no identified risks.*

Market: A major risk is that, since the training materials are available in open data, open science, the alliances of universities, universities and European research centres will be able to use the training materials developed without contacting us.

The second most important risk is related to the possibility of alliances of European universities, universities and research centres not understanding the importance of the use of the training materials for their citizen science activities.

The first risk can be mitigated through an approach by researchers from the E³UDRES² alliance to other institutions, to promote their work and explain the advantages to third parties of counting on the experience of these researchers in applying the materials. By exploring the possibilities to produce hands-on, professional training materials or an online tool, we could ensure correct and controlled use of the materials.

The second risk can be controlled by the promotion of the importance and advantages of using the training materials, by the E³UDRES² alliance researchers involved in these training materials.

Legal: the most important risk is related with the compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly regarding data privacy and intellectual property, there may be some limitations during the use of the training materials by some third parties.

To address this risk it is necessary that the researchers involved in exploiting the materials analyse in detail the legal requirements of each country, together with third parties, for each case of application of the materials. ensuring that all are complied with.

Financial and management: the most important risks is related with the lack of approval from the leadership of each partner institution involved in the agreement with third parties.

The second most important risk is related to the possible lack of interest of any partner in making an effort to ensure the continuous exploration of the training materials.

To control the first risk, it is necessary that the researchers at each institution involved in citizen science activities, more specifically, exploiting the materials, should inform their institution's leadership about the importance of establishing an agreement with third parties to explore the training materials.

To control the second risk, partners interested in continuing to exploit this result must make an additional, joint effort to keep the training materials actively exploited.

Environmental regulations: *There are no identified risks.*

Action Plan

The action plan outlines the key milestones that are going to be needed to exploit the training materials. As such, taking into account the KER analysis, an action plan is presented that will have to be followed so that this result can be exploited.

Table 7 - KER5, Action Plan

#	Task	Deadline
1	Develop and sign a collaboration agreement between the partners, including the new 3 new partners of the E ³ UDRES ² alliance.	6 months after the project.
2	Identify a set of researchers per E ³ UDRES ² alliance institution interested in using and exploiting the training materials, using the ARENA platform.	6 months after the project.
3	Frequently update the set of researchers from the previous item.	Every 6 months
4	Start promoting the training materials with other European university alliances, universities and research centres by the E ³ UDRES ² alliance researchers.	6 onths after the project.
5	Make the E ³ UDRES ² Alliance a member of European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and through it promote the training materials.	9 months after the project.
6	Periodic monitoring of the possible emergence of new training materials and training materials development by responsible team, who will be defined in the collaboration agreement.	Every 6 months.

4. Monitoring communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

The monitoring of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities was guided by the Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan (D1.4), which defined specific procedures and indicators for each work package. WP1 had the responsibility to coordinate this process, ensuring that the actions foreseen in the Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan were implemented and tracked.

According to the Grant Agreement, three key activities framed this monitoring: promoting effective communication between partners (A1), promoting communication, dissemination and exploitation to external audiences (A2), and organising a science–policy conference (A3). Activities under A1 and A2 have been fully operational since the early months of the project, while A3 is scheduled for the final phase.

The indicators established in D1.4 (nos. 51 to 56) covered areas such as the launch of the website, the activation of social media, the use of EMDESK as an internal platform, the release of press materials, and the production of the video series. Monitoring across the 36 months of the project shows that all communication and dissemination actions were implemented on time, with only minor deviations in scheduling — such as the slightly later launch of the website and the first videos. These adjustments did not compromise the overall objectives or the results achieved.

In practice, the monitoring confirmed that the project delivered the planned activities and outputs, creating the basis for the results presented in the following sections. Overall, it also shows that the project achieved or exceeded the planned communication and dissemination targets, with only minor deviations that did not compromise objectives.

4.1. Final remarks on communication, dissemination and exploitation

Results from the second reporting period confirm that the metrics set in the Grant Agreement were not only achieved but, in most cases, surpassed. The project website registered 5628 visits during this phase, corresponding to an average of 375 visits per month, well above the baseline of 20 defined in the GA.

The impact of social media activity is reflected in the growth of reach, interactions and followers across all platforms. For comparability, the analysis of “views” is based on impressions (content displays), which provide a consistent metric across platforms. During the second period, project accounts generated 37,495 impressions (around 1,785 per month, compared with the GA target of 20 visits/month), an average of 138 likes per month (target: 10), together with 2,872 link clicks, 1,015 comments and 338 shares.

Press releases were also delivered as planned: 24 in total, including 11 produced directly by the project, which generated 28 articles in regional media through the partners' communication offices and cluster projects.

The video series deserves particular mention. The GA foresaw nine videos for the entire project. By the end of the second reporting period, the project had produced 24 videos in total, of which six formed the official series and the remainder documented workshops, training sessions and dissemination activities.

Newsletters followed a similar trend. A total of 15 were published, including five issued at project level and ten by partners, surpassing the six foreseen in the GA.

Podcasts became another output of the project's dissemination. Sixteen podcast episodes were produced, creating an innovative format to share project discussions and results with wider audiences

Exploitation activities became more prominent in the second period, as results began to mature. Work on key exploitable results (KERs) created opportunities to explore how the knowledge and tools developed could be used beyond the project. Clustering with related Horizon Europe projects, citizen science workshops and the testing of engagement frameworks in academic contexts positioned results for future uptake.

Exploitation was not treated as a separate stage but as a process linked to communication and dissemination: channels gave visibility to emerging results, dissemination shared them with academic and civic communities, and exploitation prepared them for practical use. This approach increases the likelihood that the project's impact will continue beyond its formal lifetime.

Difficulties and limitations

Communication in Ent-r-e-novators also faced challenges. The project addressed a niche theme, highly relevant to academic and research communities but less visible to wider audiences. The higher education field is also saturated with European projects, making it harder to stand out. Partner institutions' communication departments influenced this dynamic: each follows its own agendas and procedures, making visibility a competitive process. At the same time, their support was crucial.

As Figure 16 showed, their contribution through earned media was one of the main ways project activities reached regional and national audiences, complementing the project's own channels.

Overall results

Despite these constraints, the second period marked a strong consolidation of results: the project built a consistent online presence, engaged both academic and civic audiences, and disseminated outputs across face-to-face events, workshops and conferences. Exploitation was also progressively integrated, linking key results to future use in education and research. Comparing the two reporting periods, the difference is clear. The first recorded 219 activities, while the second reached 985 – more than four times higher. Yet the change was not only in scale. The second period also shows a stronger link between dissemination outputs and communication efforts, particularly around major events and newsletters. While the first phase focused on building visibility and establishing structures, the second reflects a mature and coordinated approach where outputs were consistently reinforced across multiple channels.

Conclusion

Taken together, these results demonstrate that the Ent-r-e-novators project not only delivered what was foreseen in the Grant Agreement but, in most areas, surpassed those commitments. Communication and dissemination combined project-owned platforms with the institutional channels of six partner countries and, at times, additional international presences. The project was also visible in the news media, reinforcing its reach beyond academic environments. This is a specific type of project, targeting specialised audiences and addressing a niche theme, and cannot be compared with large-scale consumer campaigns. Within this context, however, performance exceeded expectations: not only were the metrics achieved, but visibility and engagement consistently remained above the baselines set at the outset. Communication and dissemination provided visibility and interaction, while exploitation prepared the ground for the future use of results. Together, these strands ensured that Ent-r-e-novators fulfilled its objectives by raising awareness, sharing knowledge and creating conditions for an impact that can extend beyond the project's lifetime.

Table 8 - Description of communication activities, target group, frequency and metrics for the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project.

Communication Activity	Frequency	Metrics (targets)	16M-36M
Virtual communication platform	Throughout the whole project duration	# of regular users (54) Feedback from users (30)	
Online presence of the project	Throughout the whole project duration	Webpage: # of visitors per month (avg 20) Social media: # of visitors per month (avg 20) # of likes/month (avg 10)	Website: 5628 visits total, avg 288/month Social media: 1672 visitors/month avg 131 likes/month
Conference	Once at the end of the project	Number and type of: - participants from the E³UDRES² (100) - stakeholders (30) - citizens (20) Total = 150	1
Press releases	Six per project year	# of press releases per partner and per year (in total 18)	36 press releases (7 project level + 29 institutional)
E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series	At least once per project year	# of videos produced/year (3) # of videos published/year (3) # of visualisations per video and per year (100)	6 videos in official series + 9 additional videos (18 total) 302 views per year
Participation in the European Researchers' Night	Once per project year	# of partners participating/year (6)	5 of partners X participating/year

5. Communication opportunities for the European Commission

Throughout the 36 months of the project, the Ent-r-e-novators project systematically highlighted the European Commission's role in supporting research and innovation. All materials produced – including the website, newsletters, press releases, videos, social media posts and event documents, roll-ups and brochures – carried the EU emblem and funding statement, as # in social media, as defined in the Grant Agreement.

Beyond formal compliance, the project created multiple opportunities to make this support visible to different audiences. At the European Researchers' Night, for example, booths and workshops hosted by the six partner institutions displayed the Horizon Europe funding message to citizens, schools and regional communities. Academic events, such as the Science and Policy Conference and the PhD Summer School, also highlighted the Commission's contribution, reaching students, researchers, and policymakers across Europe.

Digital channels amplified this visibility further. Posts across Facebook, LinkedIn, X and YouTube consistently associated project results with Horizon Europe, while institutional communication offices ensured that press releases and news items acknowledged EU funding. Shared Media also contributed to this visibility, as interactions with project content – including likes, shares, and comments – extended the reach of the Commission's role beyond the project's direct channels, embedding the EU funding message in professional and civic conversations.

As a result, the European Commission was recognised not only within the consortium but also by external audiences as a central enabler of the project's activities. In practice, this means that the Ent-r-e-novators project provided the European Commission with sustained and visible communication opportunities throughout its lifetime, combining academic, civic and digital spaces.

ANNEX | KER Priority Maps

KER Priority Maps

KER1: Network collaboration and sharing system (WP3)

Key Exploitable Results	Degree of importance of the risk related to the final achievement of this Key Exploitable Result. Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention	Feasibility/Success of intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors						
One university in the alliance no longer wants to participate in the network.	7	4	27	To do the network without partner	6	159
There are very few external institutions that want to participate in the network.	6	5		To do the network with just a few external institutions and promote the network to motivate more and more external entities to participate.	3	
The other European university alliance networks and other networks do not want to collaborate with our network.	6	4		To do the network with just a few other networks or without them and promote the network to motivate more and more alliances and other networks to participate.	6	
A university in the E2UDRES2 alliance fails to provide sufficient resources to keep the network up to date.	7	3		To do the network without partner	5	
Disagreement on ownership rules	9	4		Prepare a consortium agreement, signed by all partners, where the role of each one must be well defined and clearly defined. There should be a periodic analysis of the protocols suitability with the evolution of the network and, if necessary, its revision.	9	
Technological Risk Factors						
Server to host the platform with inefficient operation and inadequate maintenance.	10	4	31,28	Analyze who among the E2UDRES2 alliance partners will have the best solution for hosting the network, even if it is only temporarily.	9	263
Technological solution with difficulties in maintenance, updating and use.	10	3		Create a working group to monitor the performance of the network and carry out continuous analysis of other technological solutions, ensuring its maintenance and updating.	10	
Better technology emerges for this kind of network.	8	2		Create a working group to monitor the performance of the network's operation, carry out a continuous analysis of other technological solutions and, if it was decided to change the technology solution, be prepared for the change.	8	
Difficulty communicating with other internal or external networks.	8	3		Analyze the best way to communicate with other networks, use standard communication protocols and typical translators.	9	
Data Security and Protection, cyber attacks and unauthorized access to confidential data	10	5		The network must be robustly developed to address this risk, it must be continuously monitored for this risk, and the maintenance team must be competent and well prepared to intervene quickly and effectively if the risk materializes.	6	
Market Risk Factors						
Appearance of other networks with more effective and accessible technological solutions	9	7	28	Analyze the advantages of other networks and implement them in our network	7	242
Nobody uses the product. Nobody needs it.	10	1		Promote the advantages of using the network and how to use it.	8	
Exploitation disagreement: partners with divergent interests.	8	3		Create a working group for the development, maintenance and promotion of the network involving all partners with close ties to the leadership of the respective universities.	9	
Nobody uses the product. Expectations of product usefulness are not met.	7	3		Promote the advantages of using the network and how to use it and continually conduct surveys and other consultations with researchers and stakeholders to adapt the network to their expectations.	10	
Worthless result: performance lower than market needs.	9	2		Define KPIs on the network's performance and carry out continuous monitoring.	10	
IPR/legal Risk Factors						
Compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly regarding data privacy and intellectual property, poses significant challenges.	10	3	27	The development group and the maintenance group must analyze in detail all legal requirements in all countries involved, ensuring that all are complied with, on an ongoing basis.	10	258
Risk of not complying with the internal regulations of each alliance university and external stakeholders.	10	3		The development group and the maintenance group must analyze in detail all internal regulations of all partner universities and all external stakeholders, ensuring that they are all complied with, on an ongoing basis.	10	
Risks of not being up to date with new legal requirements in different countries.	10	2		The maintenance group must monitor, with appropriate frequency, changes in the legislation of the various countries involved and the regulations of the partners, and if there are changes to be made, ensure that these changes are effectively implemented and in a timely manner.	9	
Financial/management Risk Factors						
Risks of effectively managing the functioning of the network, when it is necessary to be in convergence with the management of the different partners and with their various management substructures.	10	4	26	Establish a centralised risk management team composed of representatives from each institution. This team will oversee the development and implementation of risk management policies, ensuring consistency across all partners	8	212
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step towards exploitation	10	3		Try to find external financing to guarantee the resources (national, European and private funding).	8	
Multiple changes to original objectives.	5	4		Establish periods for reviewing the network and its objectives, based on the SWOT analysis of the previous period, and only change the objectives based on this analysis and the dates planned for this.	10	
Lack of endorsement from top management	8	2		Establish a centralized risk management team made up of representatives from each institution, with strong ties to the leadership of each institution and with periodic meetings to keep the leadership updated and involved.	8	
Off time supply of financial means.	5	4		Plan in advance, at least one year in advance, all expected expenses and revenues, with the approval of the leadership of each partner, and if there is any urgent need for financing, there must be a commitment from the leadership of the partners to collaborate in its resolution.	7	
Environmental/regulatory Risk Factors						
GDPR and cross-border data protection issues when sharing AI information	4	5	13	Develop GDPR-compliant data management protocols and anonymisation tools	8	90
Differences in national regulations for research infrastructure use/procurement	3	4		Harmonise consortium policies with national AI regulations; create guidance for cross-border procedures	6	
Lack of formalised cooperation agreements with external infrastructures	4	4		Establish standardised cooperation agreements (MOUs, templates) for external infrastructures	8	
High energy demand of digital platforms/labs misaligned with EU Green Deal	3	3		Introduce energy efficiency measures and align digital tools with EU Green Deal standards	6	
Delays due to ethics approvals or lack of harmonised standards (citizen science)	2	4		Streamline ethics approval processes; create common framework for citizen science and external partners	7	

KER2: Package of training activities on OS/OI/OE (WP4)

Key Exploitable Results	Degree of importance of the risk related to the final achievement of this Key Exploitable Result. Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention	Feasibility/Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	8	3			7	
One university of the alliance does not agree to the terms to be negotiated with the third party.	2	6	29	This partner is left out of the negotiation and the agreement with the third party.	9	202
The third party only agrees to negotiate with one or a few universities in the alliance, where UPT is included	8	3		Continuation of the agreement only with partners accepted by the third party, informing the other partners that the third party has only agreed to include a limited number of partners.	8	
The third party only agrees to negotiate with one or a few universities in the alliance, where UPT is excluded.	10	2		The partners participating in the negotiation must explain to the third party that UPT's participation in the agreement is essential, or the partners must reach an agreement with UPT to provide consultancy work to the partners that are part of the agreement with the third party.	6	
A partner of the alliance does business with third parties without informing UPT if they want to participate and to lead.	9	3		After becoming aware of this problem, inform that the partner should contact UPT next time and check whether there is still a possibility of involving UPT, if interested, in the ongoing agreement.	5	
There is the possibility of making an agreement with a third party, in which UPT's participation is essential, but UPT is not interested	10	2		After becoming aware of this problem, inform that the partner should contact UPT next time and check whether there is still a possibility of involving UPT, if interested, in the ongoing agreement.	5	
A partner developing derivative materials based on the training materials without making reference to the original materials or the Ent-r.e-novators project	10	4		Partners using the projects' deliverables always mention the source of the deliverable. Also, when developing new materials these should be shared within the consortium with all partners involved	8	
A partner developing additional materials based on the original training pack without informing the other partners of the consortium.	10	4		When developing new educational resources, these should be shared within the consortium with all partners involved	8	
Technological Risk Factors	9	3			9	
As several of these training events were hybrid or online, a technological risk rely on the videoconference platform used	9	3	27	When developing new events or resources, partners must carefully select platforms that ensure GDPR compliance, utilize encryption, and implement strong legal safeguards. Organizing more in-depth events, including hands-on workshops, and developing practical guides or tutorials on specific tools can serve as enduring resources and help standardise technological approaches	9	243
Market Risk Factors	8	4			8	
More current and interesting training activities may appear.	9	3	31	ESUDRES2 Alliance researchers involved in the training activities on OS/OI/OE, should continuously monitor emerging courses and update their training activities on OS/OI/OE accordingly.	10	240
Potential users outside the E ² UDRES ² Alliance might not understand the importance of using the training materials or the value of the resulting Foundations of Open Practices Badge	8	4		Promotion of the importance and advantages of using the training materials, by the ESUDRES2 alliance researchers involved in these training materials.	7	
Most European university alliances, universities and research centers consider that their researchers already have the necessary skills in OS/OI/OE and are not interested in these activities.	7	4		There should be an approach from researchers in the ESUDRES2 alliance to other institutions to promote their work and explain to third parties the advantages of relying on the experience of these researchers to support their training activities on OS/OI/OE, not just providing courses, but also a complete support and consultancy service.	6	
Since the training materials (e.g., presentations, recordings, outcomes from interactive sessions) are available in an open framework, a major risk is that alliances of universities, universities, and European research centers may use the materials without contacting the developing partners.	9	4		E ² UDRES ² Alliance researchers should actively approach other institutions to promote their work and explain the advantages of applying the materials. The importance and benefits of using the training materials should be continually promoted. Considering the creation of hands-on, professional training materials and the existing on the materials in the Arena Learning Hub, an online tool, it could ensure correct and controlled use.	8	
IPR/Legal Risk Factors	10	4			10	
Compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly concerning GDPR compliance and data sharing. Limitations may arise during the use of the training materials by third parties, especially concerning the balance of intellectual property rights with open collaboration.	10	4	40	It is necessary that the researchers involved in exploiting the materials analyse in detail the legal requirements of each country, together with third parties, for each case of application of the materials, ensuring that all are complied with. When engaging in open innovation, especially with confidential business data, careful platform selection and legal safeguards are crucial	10	400
Financial/management Risk Factors	9	3			8	
Inadequate communication among partners.	8	2	23	Identify people and bodies in each institution responsible for or linked to the OS/OI/OE issues and establish communication channels between them. These people and bodies will ensure that all institutions are aware of current developments in this area, including exploiting the MOOC courses.	10	180
Lack of approval from the leadership of each partner institution regarding establishing exploitation agreements with third parties.	10	3		It is necessary that the researchers at each institution involved in open practices activities, more specifically exploiting the materials, should inform their institution's leadership about the importance of establishing an agreement with third parties to explore the training materials.	8	
Problems in managing the agreement with third parties.	7	3		Researchers involved in the agreement should seek support from their institutions' services, particularly legal services, to help resolve the issues.	8	
Lack of interest of any partner in making an effort to ensure the continuous exploration and maintenance of the training materials, such as updating content with open practices on AI or other emergent technologies.	10	3		Partners interested in continuing to exploit this result must make an additional, joint effort to keep the training materials actively exploited, perhaps by expanding future editions and deepening partnerships.	7	
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation.	10	2		Partners should try to find national or European funding sources that can finance the effort to maintain the exploitation of the training activities on OS/OI/OE.	7	
No resources (human and/or financial) keep the courses running and make periodic updates.	10	2		Partners should try to find national or European funding sources that can finance the effort to keep MOOC courses active and up-to-date.	7	
Environmental/regulatory Risk Factors	0	0	0		0	0

KER3: MOOC courses on OS/OI/OE (WP4)

Key Exploitable Results	Degree of importance of the risk related to the final achievement of this Key Exploitable Result. Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention	Feasibility/Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	8	3			7	
One university of the alliance does not agree to the terms to be negotiated with the third party.	2	6	29	This partner is left out of the negotiation and the agreement with the third party.	9	202
The third party only agrees to negotiate with one or a few universities in the alliance, where UPT is included.	8	3		Continuation of the agreement only with partners accepted by the third party, informing the other partners that the third party has only agreed to include a limited number of partners.	8	
The third party only agrees to negotiate with one or a few universities in the alliance, where UPT is excluded.	10	2		The partners participating in the negotiation must explain to the third party that UPT's participation in the agreement is essential, or the partners must reach an agreement with UPT to provide consultancy work to the partners that are part of the agreement with the third party.	6	
A partner of the alliance does business with third parties without informing UPT if they want to participate and to lead.	9	3		After becoming aware of this problem, inform that the partner should contact UPT next time and check whether there is still a possibility of involving UPT, if interested, in the ongoing agreement.	5	
There is the possibility of making an agreement with a third party, in which UPT's participation is essential, but UPT is not interested.	10	2		After becoming aware of this problem, inform that the partner should contact UPT next time and check whether there is still a possibility of involving UPT, if interested, in the ongoing agreement.	5	
A partner developing derivative materials based on the MOOCs without making reference to the original materials or the Ent-r.e-novators project.	10	4		Partners using the projects' deliverables always mention the source of the deliverable.	8	
A partner developing additional materials based on the original Courses without informing the other partners of the consortium.	10	4		When developing new educational resources, these should be shared within the consortium with all partners involved.	8	
Technological Risk Factors	9	3			9	
A technological risk relies on the support of the Arena Learning Hub, the digital platform used.	9	3	27	Since the MOOC courses are based on Moodle, the courses will be migrated to another server of another partner, who uses Moodle in their academic activities, while the ARENA problem is resolved.	9	243
Market Risk Factors	8	4			8	
More current and interesting MOOC courses may appear.	9	3	33	ESUDRES2 Alliance researchers involved in the MOOC courses, led by UPT, should continuously monitor emerging courses and update their MOOC courses accordingly.	10	256
Potential users outside the E ² UDRES ² Alliance might not understand the importance of using the training materials or the value of the resulting Foundations of Open Practices Badge	8	4		E ² UDRES ² Alliance researchers should actively approach other institutions to promote their work and explain the advantages of counting on the project researchers' experience in applying the materials. The importance and benefits of using the educational resources should be continually promoted by the involved E ² UDRES ² Alliance researchers.	7	
Most European university alliances, universities and research centers consider that their researchers already have the necessary skills in OS/OI/OE and are not interested in MOOC courses.	7	5		There should be an approach from researchers in the ESUDRES2 alliance to other institutions to promote their work and explain to third parties the advantages of relying on the experience of these researchers to support their MOOC courses, not just providing courses, but also a complete support and consultancy service.	6	
Since the training materials (courses and resources) are available as open data and are freely available, alliances of universities, universities, and European research centres may use the materials without contacting the developing partners	9	4		Exploring the possibility of multiply the courses on other platforms, of the institutions or professional MOOCs platforms, could help ensure correct and controlled use of the materials.	8	
IPR/Legal Risk Factors	10	4			10	
Compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly concerning GDPR compliance and data sharing	10	4	40	It is necessary that the researchers involved in accessing and re-sharing the educational resources and materials analyse in detail the legal requirements of each country, together with third parties, for each case of application of the materials, ensuring that all are complied with	10	400
Financial/management Risk Factors	9	2			8	
Inadequate communication among partners.	8	2	23	Identify people and bodies in each institution responsible for or linked to the OS/OI/OE issues and establish communication channels between them. These people and bodies will ensure that all institutions are aware of current developments in this area, including exploiting the MOOC courses.	10	177
Lack of approval from the leadership of each partner institution regarding establishing exploitation agreements with third parties.	10	3		It is necessary that the researchers at each institution involved in open practices activities, more specifically exploiting the materials, should inform their institution's leadership about the importance of establishing an agreement with third parties to explore the courses	8	
Problems in managing the agreement with third parties.	7	3		Researchers involved in the agreement should seek support from their institutions' services, particularly legal services, to help resolve the issues.	8	
There is no interest from any partner and especially from UPT in making an effort to ensure the continued exploitation of the MOOC courses	10	2		Partners interested in continuing to exploit this result should make an additional joint effort to keep MOOC courses actively exploited.	7	
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation.	10	2		Partners should try to find national or European funding sources that can finance the effort to maintain the exploitation activities of MOOC courses.	7	
No resources (human and/or financial) keep the courses running and make periodic updates.	10	2		Partners should try to find national or European funding sources that can finance the effort to keep MOOC courses active and up-to-date.	7	
Lack of interest of any partner in making an effort to ensure the continuous exploration and maintenance of the MOOCs	10	3		Partners interested in continuing to exploit this result must make an additional, joint effort to keep the MOOCs actively exploited, perhaps by expanding future editions and deepening partnerships.	8	
Environmental/regulatory Risk Factors	0	0			0	
			0			0

KER4: Maturity model for acquiring the engagement skills in Citizen Science (WP5)

Key Exploitable Results	Degree of importance of the risk related to the final achievement of this Key Exploitable Result. Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention	Feasibility/Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	6	4			7	
One university of the alliance does not agree to the terms to be negotiated with the third party.	2	6	23	This partner is left out of the negotiation and the agreement with the third party.	9	164
The third party only agrees to negotiate with one or a few universities in the alliance.	8	2		Continuation of the agreement only with partners accepted by the third party.	8	
A partner developing additional materials based on the original model without informing the other partners of the consortium.	7	3		When developing new materials these should be shared within the consortium with all partners involved in WPS.	6	
A partner developing derivative materials based on the maturity model without making reference to the original model or the Ent-r-e-novators project.	8	4		Partners using the projects' deliverables always mention the source of the deliverable	5	
Technological Risk Factors	0	0	0		0	0
Market Risk Factors	8	4			8	
The maturity model becomes obsolete due to the appearance of new, more effective models.	9	3	32	E3UDRES2 Alliance researchers involved in the maturity model, should continuously monitor emerging models and update their model accordingly.	9	245
Most of the alliances of European universities, universities and research centers do not understand the importance of the model for their citizen science.	6	5		Promotion of the importance and advantages of using the maturity model and how to use it, by the E3UDRES2 alliance researchers involved in the model	7	
As the maturity model is available in open data, open science, the alliances of universities, universities and European research centers will be able to use the maturity model developed without contacting us.	9	4		There should be an approach from researchers in the E3UDRES2 alliance to other institutions, to promote their work and explain the advantages to third parties of counting on the experience of these researchers in applying the maturity model, and also, by developing a (e.g. licence) card game, the alliance has control over the correct use the maturity model exercise. Information about the model and how to use it is open source, available online. The 'official' hands-on material can only be ordered via contacting the involved Ent-r-e-novators researchers (at UCLL).	7	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	10	3			10	
Compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly regarding data privacy and intellectual property, there may be some limitations during the use of the maturity model by some third parties.	10	3	30	It is necessary that the researchers involved in exploiting the maturity model analyse in detail the legal requirements of each country, together with third parties, for each case of application of the model, ensuring that all are complied with.	10	300
Financial/management Risk Factors	9	3			8	
Inadequate communication among partners.	8	2	22	Identify researchers at each institution interested in developing citizen science activities and establish communication channels between them. These researchers will ensure that all institutions are aware of current developments in this area, including exploiting the maturity model.	10	179
Lack of approval from the leadership of each partner institution involved in the agreement with third parties	10	3		Researchers at each institution involved in citizen science activities, more specifically exploiting the maturity model, should inform their institution's leadership about the importance of establishing an agreement with third parties to explore the model.	8	
Problems in managing the agreement with third parties.	7	3		Researchers involved in the agreement should seek support from their institutions' services, particularly legal services, to help resolve the issues.	8	
Lack of approval from the leadership of each partner institution involved in the agreement with third parties	9	3		Partners interested in continuing to exploit this result must make an additional, joint effort to keep the maturity model actively exploited.	7	
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation	9	2		Partners should try to find national or European funding sources that can finance the effort to maintain the exploitation of the active maturity model.	7	
Environmental/regulatory Risk Factors	0	0	0		0	0

KER5: Package of training activities on Citizen Science (WP5)

Key Exploitable Results	Degree of importance of the risk related to the final achievement of this Key Exploitable Result. Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention	Feasibility/Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors	6	4			7	
One university of the alliance does not agree to the terms to be negotiated with the third party.	2	6	23	This partner is left out of the negotiation and the agreement with the third party.	9	164
The third party only agrees to negotiate with one or a few universities in the alliance.	8	2		Continuation of the agreement only with partners accepted by the third party.	8	
A partner developing additional materials based on the original training pack without informing the other partners of the consortium	7	3		When developing new materials these should be shared within the consortium with all partners involved	6	
A partner developing derivative materials based on the training materials without making reference to the original materials or the Ent-r-e-novators project.	8	4		Partners using the projects' deliverables always mention the source of the deliverable	5	
Technological Risk Factors	0	0	0		0	0
Market Risk Factors	8	5			8	
The training materials becomes obsolete due to the appearance of new, more effective materials and methods.	9	4	37	E3UDRES2 Alliance researchers involved in the maturity model, especially at UCLL, should continuously monitor emerging training materials and update their materials accordingly.	9	286
Most of the alliances of European universities, universities and research centers do not understand the importance of training its researchers to develop activities on citizen science.	6	5		An approach by researchers from the E3UDRES2 alliance to other institutions, to promote their work and explain the advantages to third parties of counting on the experience of these researchers in applying the materials. By exploring the possibilities to produce hands-on, professional training materials or an online tool, we could ensure correct and controlled use of the materials	7	
As the training materials are available in open data, open science, the alliances of universities, universities and European research centres will be able to use the training materials developed without contacting us	9	5		Promotion of the importance and advantages of using the training materials, by the E3UDRES2 alliance researchers involved in these training materials	7	
IPR/legal Risk Factors	10	4	40		10	400
Compliance with diverse national and international legal frameworks, particularly regarding data privacy and intellectual property, there may be some limitations during the use of the training materials by some third parties	10	4		It is necessary that the researchers involved in exploiting the materials analyse in detail the legal requirements of each country, together with third parties, for each case of application of the materials, ensuring that all are complied with.	10	
Financial/management Risk Factors	9	3			8	
Inadequate communication among partners.	8	2	22	Identify researchers at each institution interested in developing citizen science activities and establish communication channels between them. These researchers will ensure that all institutions are aware of current developments in this area, including exploiting training activities.	10	179
Lack of approval from the leadership of each partner institution involved in the agreement with third parties	10	3		Researchers at each institution involved in citizen science activities, more specifically exploiting the training activities, should inform their institution's leadership about the importance of establishing an agreement with third parties to explore the training activities.	8	
Problems in managing the agreement with third parties.	7	3		Researchers involved in the agreement should seek support from their institutions' services, particularly legal services, to help resolve the issues.	8	
Lack of interest of any partner in making an effort to ensure the continuous exploration of the training materials	9	3		partners interested in continuing to exploit this result must make an additional, joint effort to keep the training materials actively exploited.	7	
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation	9	2		Partners should try to find national or European funding sources that can finance the effort to maintain the exploitation of the training activities.	7	
Environmental/regulatory Risk Factors	0	0	0		0	0

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